

The Role of Project Management Competencies on Project Success in the Rail Industry

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Business Administration (MBA) in the University of Durham

By

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This dissertation is the result of my own work. Material from the published or unpublished work of others, which is referred to in the dissertation is credited to the author in question in the text. The dissertation is 22,198 words in total. Research ethics issues have been considered and handled appropriately within the Durham Business School guidelines and procedures.

ABSTRACT

Project management as a profession and method of organising working has grown exponentially in the last 20-30 years across a broad spectrum of industries. The ability of organisations to successfully implement projects is critical to their ability to meet their strategic objectives, as demonstrated by the growing reliance on project management as a method of organising work. Despite the application of project management as a method of working, many projects fail to achieve expected outcomes.

This study was an exploratory mixed methods research to examine whether project management competencies impact project success; and to identify the competencies which are most crucial to success in complex rail infrastructure projects.

Chapter one introduced the topic and presented the background and statement of the problem that warranted this research.

Literature review provided an overview of recent developments in the project management field as well as an in-depth discussion on the meaning of 'project success'. This was followed by an exploration of some of the extant literature on the impact of project management competencies and leadership skills on project outcomes. Secondary research findings indicated that the acceptance and growing popularity of project management as a discipline does not automatically improve project success rates. Researchers tend to agree that whilst the technical aspects or dimension of project management are important, it is the behavioural competencies or soft skills of project managers which are required for success.

The primary research explored the perceptions of participants in two organisations involved in complex large-scale rail projects in South East England. The primary research was completed via survey. Follow-up semi-structured interviews were conducted to validate the survey results.

Research indicated that the application of technical project management tools and techniques alone does not ensure projects will achieve successful outcomes; but rather competent leadership, communication skills, stakeholder management as well as prior relevant experience are perceived to be essential to project success.

Conclusions and implications of the research findings were presented and recommendations for further research given.

The study was evaluated against the research objectives with the conclusion that these were achieved.

Keywords: Competencies, Complex Infrastructure Projects, Leadership Skills, Project Management, Project Manager, Project Success, Project Success Factors, Technical Project Management Skills, Rail Industry.

DEDICATION

This dissertation is dedicated to the memory of my late father – Mr Reuben Idahosa Osagie. His love for education and self development have been inspirational all my life and instilled in me the desire and drive to acquire knowledge, and the drive to pursue my goals in life.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	3
DEDICATION	5
ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	6
LIST OF FIGURES	9
LIST OF TABLES	10
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	11
1:1 Background to the Study	11
1:2 Statement of the Problem	12
1:3 TFL's Challenge	12
1:4 Aims and Objectives of the Dissertation	13
1:5 Rationale.....	14
1:6 Research Questions.....	14
1:7 Significance of the Dissertation	15
1:8 Nature of the Dissertation	15
1:9 Scope of the Dissertation	15
1:10 Structure of the Remainder of the Dissertation	16
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW.....	17
2:1 Introduction	17
2:2 Definition of Key Terms.....	17
2:3 Literature Review on Project Management.....	19
2:4 Project Success	20
2.4.1 Project Management Success	22
2.4.2 Project Success vs. Product Success.....	23
2.4.3 Project Success vs. Business Success.....	24
2.4.4 Project Success and Stakeholder Satisfaction.....	24
2:5 Project Success - Summary	25
2:6 Project Success Factors	25
2:7 Project Managers' Leadership Competence as Project Success Factor.....	27
2:8 Project Management Competencies for Complex Rail Infrastructure Projects	29
2:9 Conclusion of Literature Review.....	32
CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	34
3:1 Introduction	34
3:2 Primary Research Methodology	34
3:3 Research Questions.....	37

3:4 Research Instruments	37
3:5 Pilot Study.....	38
3:6 Population and Sample Size	38
3:7 Data Collection Procedures and Analysis Method	39
3:8 Validity and Reliability	43
3:9 Ethical Considerations	44
3:10 Summary	45
CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS.....	46
4:1 Overview	46
4:2 Questionnaire Results and Analysis	46
4:3 Project Management Competencies	51
4:4 Top 5 Project Managers' competencies	58
4:5 Key Success Factors	59
4:6 Survey Themes.....	60
4:7 Interview Results and Analysis.....	61
4:8 Project Success	61
4:9 Project Management Competencies and Project Success	62
4:10 Project Manager Leadership Attributes and Project Success	63
4:11 Other Project Success Factors in the Rail Industry.....	65
4:12 Project Managers' Leadership Training and Development	66
4:13 Assumptions & Limitations	67
4:14 Summary	68
CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	70
5:1 Conclusion	70
5:2 Implications	73
5:3 Recommendations for Future Research	75
BIBLIOGRAPHY AND REFERENCES	76
APPENDIX	82
Appendix A: Informed Consent - Participants 18 Years of Age and Older	82
Appendix B: MBA Dissertation Questionnaire	84
Appendix C: Semi-Structured Interview Guide	91
Appendix D: Survey Participants Demographics	93
Appendix E: Session 4 Of Questionnaire Results.....	95
Appendix F: Delivery Schedule For TfL's Key Infrastructure Schemes.....	96
Appendix G: London Underground Schedule of Projects	97
Appendix H: Shenhar et al.'s (1997) Multi-Dimensional Framework of Project Success.....	98
Appendix I: Evolution of Leadership Theories	100

List of Figures

Figure 1: Transport for London's Modal Structure	11
Figure 2: PMI Nine Knowledge Areas	18
Figure 3: Project Triple Constraints	21
Figure 4: Relationship between project management competence and organisational performance	32
Figure 5: Figure showing Participants' discipline	48
Figure 6: Breakdown of Questionnaire Response on Average Project Complexity	49
Figure 7: Distribution of Questionnaire Response on Project Experience.....	50
Figure 8: Distribution of Questionnaire Response on Average Project Team Size	50
Figure 9: Distribution of Questionnaire Response on Average Monetary Value	50
Figure 10: Comparison of Results to Questions 12 and 36 of Survey.....	55
Figure 11: Emerging Themes from Questionnaire Responses on the Competencies for Successful Project Management in the Rail Industry.....	60
Figure 12: Relationship between project management competence and organisational performance	74

List of Tables

Table 1: Summary of TfL’s Modal Investment Expenditure	12
Table 2: Belassi and Tukul’s Lists of Critical Success Factors developed in the Literature..	26
Table 3: Competencies for Successful Projects	31
Table 4: Quantitative, Qualitative and Mixed Methods Procedures	35
Table 5: Differences between Qualitative and Quantitative Research Methods.....	36
Table 6: Breakdown of Questionnaire Participants’ Demographics by discipline	47
Table 7: Breakdown of Questionnaire Participants’ Demographics by Gender	48
Table 8: Breakdown of Questionnaire Participants’ Demographics by education	48
Table 9: Results of Section Two of Survey Questionnaire.....	52
Table 10: Results of answers to Question 12 of Survey	55
Table 11: Results of answers to Question 36 of Survey	55
Table 12: Results to Questions 14, 16, 17, 19, 21, 22, 28 & 29 of Survey	56
Table 13: Competencies “Not Listed” by Researcher	58
Table 14: Top 5 Competencies	58
Table 15: Top 3 Success Factors.....	59
Table 16: Responses to Interview Question 2	62
Table 17: Responses to Interview Question 5	65
Table 18: Top 5 Project Management Competencies.....	73

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

This study explores the project management competencies which lead to successful implementation of complex large-scale rail infrastructure projects; with a view that organisations who undertake ‘major infrastructure projects’ will benefit from this knowledge as they implement capital programmes in transport infrastructure.

1:1 Background to the Study

Transport for London (TfL), part of the Greater London Authority, is the integrated body responsible for the planning, delivery and day-to-day operation of London’s public transport network. TfL’s role is to implement the Mayor of London’s transport strategy and manage public transport services across Greater London in different modes including underground rail (popularly known as the Tube), overground rail, buses, major roads, river services and taxi & minicab regulation for which the Mayor has ultimate responsibility (Travers, 2005 & TfL 2012). The Mayor of London sets TfL’s budget and appoints the Board, which he also chairs. The modal structure of TfL is depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Transport for London’s Modal Structure

Source: Daniels (2012)

1:2 Statement of the Problem

Over the last 5 years, the scale and complexity of TfL's capital investment programme has grown as a result of the acquisition of the former public private partnership (PPP) firms, Metronet Ltd and Tube Lines Ltd (TfL, 2011). The level of investment in transport infrastructure in London, particularly the Tube, has grown significantly and many major improvement programmes are now underway; with some already delivering benefits to the public, such as the Victoria Line and Jubilee Line Upgrade Projects. All these upgrades to the existing systems are being undertaken whilst maintaining and improving day-to-day operational performance for an increasing number of passengers (TfL, 2011).

TfL plans to spend approximately £1.6bn per annum on the renewal and upgrade of the Underground network and a total of £15bn between 2009/10 and 2017/18 as shown in the table below.

Table 1: Summary of TfL's Modal Investment Expenditure

Mode	£m									
	2009/10	2010/11	2011/12	2012/13	2013/14	2014/15	2015/16	2016/17	2017/18	Total 2009/10 - 2017/18
London Underground	1,599	1,834	1,609	1,688	1,617	1,591	1,548	1,713	1,901	15,099
Surface Transport	513	534	464	455	443	432	391	379	388	4,002
London Rail	644	324	17	19	10	10	11	11	11	1,027
Crossrail cash commitment*	694	1,052	1,410	2,049	2,437	2,062	1,481	549	1,022	12,757
Corporate	248	370	331	471	272	158	150	136	139	2,276
Total	3,698	4,118	3,832	4,682	4,779	4,254	3,580	2,787	3,461	35,191

Source: (TfL Investment Programme 2010)

1:3 TFL's Challenge

TfL plans to upgrade most of the existing Tube network, whilst carrying increasing number of passengers every year and achieve efficiency savings and justify central government's investment funds in future upgrades (TfL, 2012).

The recent global economic recession that started in 2008 has heightened the need for all public sector organisations in the UK including TfL to achieve efficiency savings and justify government

funding. TfL programme and project managers are therefore expected to deliver major infrastructure projects with available resources and to strict performance and budget parameters.

These planned upgrades and renewal work will be delivered through multi-million pound major programmes and projects undertaken over the next ten years across the different transport modes as described in Appendix F and G of this study.

According to industry reports by Railnews (2013), plans to invest over £25 billion in over 200 major rail projects over the next seven years are at risk because the rail industry faces a growing difficulty in recruiting suitably qualified and experienced staff (Railnews, 2013).

The increase in TfL's in-house project delivery has led to an increased focus on enhancing the organisation's project management capability. There is also focus on training of project management resources on what Cooke-Davies and Arzymanow (2003) refer to as the technical dimension of project management; through the Accredited Project Professional (APP) scheme and Health, Safety and Environment (HSE) courses which sets minimum professional and competency standards for project managers in the organisation (Olaghere, 2012).

Poor project delivery performance has adverse consequences for organisations such as TfL who invest billions in capital programmes every year. The UK Central government, which partly funds TfL, need constant assurance that public money is being spent wisely with tangible benefits for the public. Also mismanaged or delayed projects have adverse impact on other stakeholder groups such as customers and end users of London's public transport network who may well have to endure station and line closures and suffer major disruption to their journeys during the course of station and line upgrades.

1:4 Aims and Objectives of the Dissertation

The purpose of the study is to explore project management competencies that lead to successful implementation of complex large-scale rail infrastructure projects. This study has been completed with

a view that organisations will benefit from this knowledge as they implement major capital programmes across a wide range of industries, especially those engaged in major infrastructure projects of any type.

1:5 Rationale

The ability of organisations to successfully implement projects is critical to their ability to meet their strategic objectives, as shown by the growing reliance on project management as a method of organising work (Cooke-Davies & Arzymanow, 2003; Golob, 2002 & Morris & Pinto, 2004). The aim of this study is to fill a gap in the project management literature with regards to the role of project management competencies in achieving successful project outcomes in the rail industry.

Many studies describe the key success factors for projects (Cooke-Davies, 2002; De Wit 1988). What is lacking is an examination of the reality of projects in the rail industry by studying the experiences of those involved in delivering complex rail projects.

This study examines project managers' competencies as a critical project success factor. Although much is written on project success factors, little is written about the relationship of the project manager's competency to that success (Turner & Müller, 2005). Both hard and soft skills play a crucial role in determining the success of a project (Thite, 1999). A comprehensive review of the literature in this area is presented in chapter two of this study.

1:6 Research Questions

With primary questions on what the essential competencies of an effective project manager in the rail industry are, a series of research questions were developed through detailed secondary research to identify gaps in the literature.

1:7 Significance of the Dissertation

The output of the research will add to the body of knowledge in the project management field by identifying the elements of project managers' competencies and behaviours that lead to better project outcomes or success within the context of complex rail infrastructure projects.

The results of the study will also provide leaders within the rail and other industries with the knowledge and insights necessary to implement changes and establish best practices for training project management resources to reduce the rates of challenged and failed projects.

1:8 Nature of the Dissertation

This research is an exploratory mixed methods study. The researcher's primary instruments of data collection were questionnaires and semi-structured interviews.

The main interest of the primary study is to examine the perception of participants regarding project managers' competencies within Transport for London. However, it was felt that useful data could be found by considering other project-based organisations in the rail industry. The researcher therefore solicited project professionals in other organisations such as Network Rail and Bombardier Transportation UK (BTUK) for additional primary data required in order to increase the general application of the findings.

1:9 Scope of the Dissertation

The primary focus of this study is on the role of project managers' competencies and behaviours on project outcomes. The level of organisational project management competency is not examined, but rather the dynamics of the project team and project managers' competencies within the context of rail infrastructure projects.

The competencies or behaviours of other key players within the project teams, such as project sponsor, are not investigated in this study.

1:10 Structure of the Remainder of the Dissertation

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows:

Chapter Two presents a review of existing literature on project management development, as well as project success criteria and project success factors. This secondary research is used to identify gaps in the literature and frame the primary research questions. Chapter Three describes the research methodology, including the design, population and sample selection, data collection and analysis procedures. Chapter Four presents the results and discusses the findings from the primary research. Finally, Chapter Five presents conclusions, implications for the practice of project management and recommendations for further research.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2:1 Introduction

This chapter presents an in-depth review of the extant literature on project management relevant to the present study. Following the definition of key terms, the paper discusses recent developments in the field of project management and what constitutes project success with reference to both academic and management literature. This is followed by consideration of the impact of project managers' leadership competencies on project outcomes and competencies required for successful project delivery.

The secondary research findings are used as a framework for the primary research that follows in chapter three.

2:2 Definition of Key Terms

Competence

According to the European Guide to Good Practice in Knowledge Management (2003 in Hessami & Moore, 2007), competence is an appropriate blend of knowledge, experience and motivational factors which enables a person to perform a task successfully. In other words, "*competence is the ability to perform a task correctly, efficiently and consistently to a high quality under varying conditions, to the satisfaction of the end client*" (Hessami & Moore, 2007).

Competency

Competency can be defined as "*knowledge, skills, and personal attributes that lead to superior results or to meet defined performance standards*" (Turner & Muller, 2005).

Competence is a widely used term often used interchangeably with competency. This is deemed acceptable within the context of this study as the definitions are similar.

Leadership

O'Reilly et al (2010), define leadership as a person's ability to influence a group to achieve organisational goals.

Projects

Tuckwood (2011) defines a project as “a unique set of co-ordinated activities, with definite starting and finishing points, undertaken by an individual or organisation to meet specific objectives within defined time, cost and performance parameters”.

Project Management

The Association for Project Management (APM, 2006) defines project management as “the process by which projects are defined, planned, monitored, controlled and delivered such that the agreed benefits are realised”.

The Project Management Institute (PMI) identifies the basic values and methodology that frame project management. These values and principles are structured around nine knowledge areas: integration, scope, time, cost, quality, human resources, communications, risk and procurement management, which are represented in the figure below:

Figure 2: PMI Nine Knowledge Areas

Project Manager

The PMI (2004) define a project manager as the person responsible for achieving the project goals and objectives. They are the chief architects and executives in charge of overseeing the day-to-day project operations.

Project Lifecycle

Jugdev & Muller, (2005) define project lifecycle as "*a collection of generally sequential project phases whose name and number are determined by the control needs of the organization or organizations involved in the project*".

Stakeholders

PMI (2004) define project stakeholders as "*individuals and organizations that are actively involved in the project, or whose interests may be affected as a result of project execution or project completion*". Typical stakeholders on projects are: project manager, customers/users, project team members, project management team, project sponsor, and optionally the PMO (PMI, 2004).

2:3 Literature Review on Project Management

Project management as a profession and method of organising working has grown exponentially in the last 20-30 years across a broad spectrum of industries (Shenhar et al, 1997; Golob, 2002; Cooke-Davies & Arzymanow, 2003; Morris & Pinto, 2004; Kendra & Taplin, 2004a; Jugdev & Muller, 2005 and Crawford, 2005).

Morris & Pinto (2004) trace the development of modern project management techniques and methodologies to between 1955 and 1969. Since its emergence as a field of practice in a few industries in the 1950s, the discipline has broadened and is now a dominant method of organising work in across a range of diverse industries from insurance and manufacturing to utilities and software engineering (Morris & Pinto, 2004).

Morris & Pinto (2004), assert that the economic, technological and social forces that shape the world today are creating an environment that increasingly leans towards a project-based approach to getting things done. This is evident from the hundreds of organisations (private and public) that are implementing their operating models as project-based working, thousands of new members enrolling every year in project management professional organisations and more universities offering degrees and qualifications on the subject of project management (Morris & Pinto, 2004).

Zimmerer & Yasin (1998) argue that project management is vital to the successful implementation of business process re-engineering, with project managers at the centre in the introduction and implementation of operational and managerial changes. The concept of project management has evolved as a means of completing projects, to a widely used business process as a means of achieving organisational goals and objectives and gaining a competitive advantage over rivals (Zimmerer & Yasin, 1998 and Jugdev & Muller, 2005).

Despite the application of project management as a method of working, many projects fail to achieve expected outcomes (Golob, 2002; Cooke-Davies, 2002; and Ojiako et al. 2008). The acceptance and growing popularity of project management as a discipline does not automatically improve project success rates.

2:4 Project Success

Few topics are more central to project management than the concept of “project success”. But project success is complex and ambiguous. Cooke-Davies (2005) notes that measuring project success or getting a unanimous definition of the term is difficult due to the differing interests and expectations of diverse stakeholder groups involved in any given project; as well as the subjective nature of the perceptions of “success”.

Similarly, Jugdev & Muller, (2005, p. 19) equate getting a unanimous definition of project success to “*gaining a consensus from a group of people on the definition of good art*”. They assert that measures of project success are very subjective, as it connotes different things to different people, at different

times (Shenhar et al., 1997 and Jugdev & Muller, 2005). Therefore context is important when discussing project success.

The APM (2006) states that project success *“is the satisfaction of stakeholder needs and is measured by the success criteria as identified and agreed at the start of the project”*. Thus, although a project may be viewed as successful by the project team when the triple constraints of time, cost and quality have been achieved, it really is not successful if stakeholder needs have not be met and the potential benefits realised.

Early on in the development of project management research, project success was defined by the criteria of time, cost and scope/quality parameters (Cooke-Davies, 2004; De Wit, 1988). These success criteria referred to as “triple constraints” within project management literature were widely used as the basis for measuring project success. As such, a project was deemed successful if it came in on time, budget and performed as expected (Pinto & Slevin, 1988). This early definition of project success was focussed on the project execution or implementation phase of the project lifecycle (Jugdev & Muller, 2005) and is represented diagrammatically below:

Figure 3: Project Triple Constraints

However, since the 1980s, studies began to reflect a shift away from the traditional triple constraints criteria to other measures of project success which included client satisfaction (Jugdev & Muller, 2005) and a distinction drawn between “project success” and “project management success”.

Shenhar et al (2007) argue that the success of a project cannot be solely measured by meeting the goals of traditional triple constraints scope, time and resources but rather it is a strategic link that connects the final service/product to the end-users' satisfaction. Shenhar developed a multi-dimensional framework of project success encompassing four dimensions - project efficiency, impact on the customer, business and direct success and preparing for the future. Appendix H provides details of Shenhar's "multi-dimensional framework".

The next sections discuss the different approaches to project success.

2.4.1 Project Management Success

De Wit (1988) and Munns and Bjeirmi (1996) argue that when attempting to measure project success, a distinction must be drawn between "project success" and "project management success". They state that although related terms, the two are essentially different, as the former refers to the degree to which the overall project objectives have been met, whilst the latter tends to be restricted to traditional measures of cost, time and quality performance (i.e. one is about the benefits from the outcomes; the other is about the project management alone).

Munns and Bjeirmi (1996, p.82) define a project as "*achievement of a specific objective, which involves a series of activities and tasks which consume resources*", and project management as the "*processes of controlling the achievement of the project objectives*". Consequently, they assert that project management is a subset of project success.

Therefore, a project can be a success despite poor project management practices and performance and vice versa. For example, the Thames Barrier project in the UK took twice as long to build and cost four times the original budget but was still considered a success by some of the contractors who took part in the project (Wateridge, 1995).

Conversely, the project management process maybe effective but still result in a failed project. For example, a project which was managed efficiently but eventually does not meet customer or organisational expectations (Shenhar et al, 1997). For example, the Millennium Dome in London was

delivered to time and budget requirement but in the eyes of the end users – the British public, the project was considered a failure as it did not deliver the “awe and glamour” that it was meant to generate (Dimitrios, 2009).

De Wit (1988) and Munns & Bjeirmi (1996), suggest that good project management techniques and practices can be employed to drive project success, but it by no means guarantees it and projects may fail if, for example, the project was flawed from the outset. Munns and Bjeirmi, (1996), concluded that the client should have more of the responsibility for project success since some of the factors which contribute to project success are outside the remit of project management and therefore outside the direct control of the project manager.

Another useful distinction was made by Cooke-Davies (2004). According to him, success criteria are the measures against which the success or failure of a project will be judged. These must be differentiated against success factors – discussed in section 2:7, which are the inputs to the management systems that lead to the success of the project. Cooke-Davies (2002) in his research titled “the real success factors of projects” proposed measuring project success along three dimensions: project management success, project success and consistent project success (business success).

2.4.2 Project Success vs. Product Success

Baccarini (1999) also made a distinction between product success and project management success. He proposed that project success consists of two components: product success and project management success. He stated that product success deals with the effects of a project’s end product, whilst project management deals with delivering outputs.

In the same vein, Jugdev and Muller (2005) suggest that project success be expanded beyond the earlier focus on the implementation phase (triple constraint criteria) to success over the project and product lifecycle. They assert that project management can have strategic value when there is a linkage between an effective project management process and how the project’s output provides

business value (project success). They argue that if, however, project success is limited to cost, schedule and scope metrics, then there is no linkage and project management will be perceived as providing tactical or operational value only and not strategic value.

2.4.3 Project Success vs. Business Success

Allport et al (2008) in their analysis of 22 case studies of rail infrastructure projects across several countries, define project success from the perspective of the promoter of the project; which in their view was the government or public authority in each country. According to them, project success is measured by financial, policy and durability success. They considered a project successful where the final cost of delivering the project compares favourably with forecasts made at the onset, delivers the policy commitment or intentions made at the beginning and finally the ability of the project to maintain its service delivery over the medium or long term.

2.4.4 Project Success and Stakeholder Satisfaction

Pinto and Slevin (1988) proposed that project success is “composed of both internal (project) factors and external (client) factors”. They identify internal project factors as those factors which the project manager has control over: time, cost and performance/scope; whilst the external client factors are user satisfaction and effectiveness.

De Wit (1988) emphasised the importance of meeting project stakeholders’ objectives in order to achieve project success. De Wit (1988) referred to Baker et al (1983)’s definition of project success thus:

“the project is considered an overall success if the project meets the technical performance specification and/or mission to be performed, and if there is a high level of satisfaction concerning the project outcome among key people in the parent organization, key people in the project team and key users or clientele of the project effort”.

Similarly, Baccarini (1999) stressed the importance of establishing customer satisfaction as a measure of success. He suggests that the project management team must identify and meet

stakeholder needs and expectations to ensure a successful project. The author referred to research by Wateridge (1995) on IT project success which highlighted the tendency of project managers to interpret project success as meeting budget and schedule (project management success) as opposed to reliability and delivering a product which end users are happy with (product success).

This new dimension to project success, according to De Wit (1988), Baccarini (1999), Jugdev and Muller (2005) and Shenhar et al. (2007), takes into consideration the need to link project management process and the project's final product.

2:5 Project Success - Summary

From the above discussion, it is clear that there is no unanimous definition or consistent approach to project success. De Wit (1988) and Cooke-Davies (2004) observe that the complexity in conceptualising the term "project success" is due to the differing objectives during different phases of the project lifecycle and a plethora of stakeholders with sometimes conflicting interests and criteria for success.

Project success is no longer to be confined to the triple constraints criteria of scope, schedule and cost; rather, it is a strategic link that connects the project outputs to end-user's satisfaction (Shenhar et al., 2007) targeted at achieving overall project goal (project success).

The focus of the study is on the role of project management competencies on successful project outcomes. Project success when used in this paper means project success as conceptualised by De Wit (1988) and Munns and Bjeirmi (1996), which includes project management success.

The following section reviews project success factors.

2:6 Project Success Factors

Regardless of what criteria are used to assess project success, Cooke-Davies (2002 & 2004) observes that a large number of projects are judged unsuccessful. This view is supported by other

authors and researchers who note the high failure rate of projects both in information technology and construction projects (Golob, 2002; Cooke-Davies, 2002; and Ojiako et al. 2008).

Cooke-Davies (2002 & 2004) argues that if project management as a field of practice is to advance, then practices and techniques that lead to success must be encouraged over those that lead to failure. It is therefore pertinent to review the literature on project success factors.

Cooke-Davies, (2002) suggest that identifying success factors is dependent on answering three separate questions: “what factors lead to project management success?”, “what factors lead to a successful project?” and “what factors lead to consistently successful projects?” Only by evaluating the answer to each of these three questions can the real success factors be determined.

Pinto and Slevin (1988) in their study identified the project manager as having a key effect on project success. Subsequently, many studies have examined project critical success factors (Belassi and Tukel, 1996; and Crawford, 2001; and Christenson & Walker, 2004). Belassi and Tukel (1996) following a review of the project management literature compiled a table of critical success factors developed in the literature by different scholars.

The table below summaries the project success factors identified by various researchers:

Table 2: Belassi and Tukel’s Lists of Critical Success Factors developed in the Literature

Martin (1976)	Locke (1984)	Cleland and King (1983)	Sayles and Chandler (1971)	Baker, Murphy and Fisher (1983)	Pinto and Slevin (1989)	Morris and Hough (1987)
Define goals	Make project	Project summary	Project manager's competence	Clear goals	Top management support	Project objectives
Select project organisational philosophy	Project authority from the top	Operational concept	Scheduling	Goal commitment of project team	Client consultation	Technical uncertainty innovation
General management support	Appoint competent project manager	Top management support	Control systems and responsibilities	On-site project manager	Personnel recruitment	Politics
Organise and delegate authority	Set up communications and procedures	Financial support	Monitoring and feedback	Adequate funding to completion	Technical tasks	Community involvement
Select project team	Set up control mechanisms	Logistic requirements	Continuing involvement in the project	Adequate project team capability	Client acceptance	Schedule duration urgency
Allocate sufficient resources	Progress meetings	Facility support		Accurate initial cost estimates	Monitoring and feedback	Financial contract legal problems

Martin (1976)	Locke (1984)	Cleland and King (1983)	Sayles and Chandler (1971)	Baker, Murphy and Fisher (1983)	Pinto and Slevin (1989)	Morris and Hough (1987)
Provide for control and information mechanism		Market intelligence		Minimum start-up difficulties	Communication	Implement problems
Require planning and review		Project schedule		Planning and control techniques	Trouble shooting	
		Executive development and training		Task (vs. Social orientation)	Characteristics of the project team leader	
		Manpower and organisation		Absence of bureaucracy	Power and politics	
		Acquisition			Environment events	
		Information and communication channels			Urgency	

Source: Belassi and Tukel (1996)

Some of the most common success factors identified across the board include: clear goals and project objectives, top management support, effective information and communication channels, the allocation of sufficient project resources, planning and control techniques and adequate project team capability.

2:7 Project Managers' Leadership Competence as Project Success Factor

There are many schools of thought on leadership and it is one of the most studied aspects of human behaviour which is reflected in the plethora of writings on the subject (Geoghegan & Dulewicz, 2008). A review of literature shows ever evolving schools of thought on the nature of leadership and the characteristics of effective leadership.

In general management literature, leadership forms a significant body of knowledge but this study focuses on project managers' leadership competencies and its impact on project outcomes within the context of rail infrastructure projects in TfL. Bolden et al. (2003) summarise the main approaches to the study of leadership found in Appendix J.

Numerous researchers have used leadership theories to enhance our understanding of the role of project manager (Pinto & Slevin, 1988; Shenhar et al, 1997; Zimmerer and Yasin, 1998; Prabhakar, 2005; and Turner & Müller, 2005).

Zimmerer and Yasin (1998), following their research into the leadership profile of American project managers, reported that the top three characteristics of effective project managers were: leadership by example, visionary and technical competence. They also found that the primary reasons projects came over budget and schedule were the failure to use appropriate tools to manage the project and poor project leadership. They suggest that *“successful projects are led by individuals who possess a blend of technical and management knowledge, but beyond both, leadership skills”*.

Prabhakar (2005) following his research of leadership in project management practices on 153 projects across 28 countries concluded that: *“effective project manager leadership is an important success factor on projects. The capabilities of the people involved in resolving extraordinary situations and unforeseen problems are an important key for project success”*.

Similarly, Selg and Rihel (2007) found evidence indicating that success of a project relies upon project leadership and its ability to get things done effectively through others. Selg and Rihel (2007) suggested that highly successful projects are led by highly effective project managers and stated that *“leadership is important to the successful completion of a project because leadership is essentially about motivating people”* (Selg and Rihel, 2007, pm.05.2).

On the other hand, Pomfret (2008), noted that practitioners of project management tend to dismiss the importance of leadership, instead they relied on the application of project processes, tools, and techniques to improve project outcomes.

The PMI commissioned Turner & Müller in 2005 to determine (1) whether the competence, including personality and leadership style, of the project manager is a success factor for projects; and (2) if different competence profiles are appropriate for different project types. They carried out an extensive review of the general management literature and management literature and found that, whilst there is

a consensus in the general management literature that effective leadership is a critical success factor for individual and organisational performance, in contrast, the project management literature hardly mentions the project managers' leadership style or competence as a success factor on projects (Turner & Müller, 2005).

Turner and Muller (2005) concluded that the project management literature largely ignored the impact of the project manager, their leadership style and competencies on project success and called for more research.

This dissertation can now turn to applying this research to its application to infrastructure projects, drawing on additional research on competency requirements and using rail infrastructure projects as an example.

2:8 Project Management Competencies for Complex Rail Infrastructure Projects

Industry reports by Railnews (2013) indicate that there will be skills shortage in the UK rail infrastructure industry due to a large number of projects being planned across the UK. For example, TfL plans to embark on major rail projects spending an estimated £15billion over the next 10 years. Appendix F and G shows a breakdown of the proposed capital investment being planned by TfL and London Underground respectively.

Schlick (1988) found in his market research of 300 training directors and education co-ordinators across various industries in the US that 80% of respondents expressed an interest in project management training. And 60% of respondents believed that project management will be a more important skill in the future.

Cooke-Davies & Arzymanow (2003,) suggest that project management has two dimensions – a technical dimension and a human dimension. According to them,

“the technical dimension encompasses those groups of practices or processes that are integral to project management, while the human dimension includes not only the people who

are operating these processes, but their expertise... taken together, these two dimensions, the human and the technical, will coalesce in a corporate culture that either promotes good project management practice, or that inhibits it".

Managing a project is a difficult task which requires a combination of technical knowledge and an ability to work with a variety of stakeholders across the organisation (Avots, 1969). Pinto and Kharbanda (1995) suggest that managing projects is a unique challenge which requires a blend of strategy and methodology, but mostly importantly requires project managers to function as leaders.

According to Crawford (2005), the competence of project managers is a subject of concern to both individuals in terms of evidencing ability for career development and businesses, as a vital element of corporate performance. The view expressed by some managers is that, the key to project success is choosing the right project manager (Crawford, 2005).

Individuals with technical and managerial skills and knowledge are sometimes thrown into the role of project manager without have a pre-determined career choice and sometimes without the appropriate training to support their development (Pinto & Kharbanda, 1995; Pellegrinelli & Garagna, 2010). Ensworth (2003) refers to these groups of people as "accidental project managers".

Pellegrinelli & Garagna (2010) also assert that many organisations do not have clear and well established career paths for project managers and competency frameworks based on rigorous research that maybe used in making selection or career progressions decisions. And even where competency frameworks are in place, the competence of project managers is usually based on the subjective assessments of their line managers.

In a study by Krahn and Hartment (2006), project management experts from various industries were asked to identify the most important skills and competencies for effective project leadership in large projects, high uncertainty projects and very novel projects. The skills are listed in the table below:

Table 3: Competencies for Successful Projects

Large Projects	High Uncertainty Projects	Very Novel Projects
Leadership	Leadership	Leadership
Relevant prior experience	Risk management	Self confidence
Planning	Planning	Having visions and goals
People skills	People skills	People skills
Verbal communication	Verbal communication	Listening skills
Team building skills	Expectations management	Expectations management

Adapted from: Krahn and Hartment, 2006

Similarly, Posner (1987) in his research into what makes a good project manager, found that communication, organisational, leadership, team building and coping skills were ranked above technological skills by participants in a project management seminar. According to Posner, these findings indicate that the primary problems of project managers are more human than technical.

This is supported by El-Sabaa's (2001) findings from his study into the skills of an effective project manager in information systems projects, electricity projects, and agricultural projects; that human skills of project managers have the most significant influence on project management practices.

Whilst there has been a lot of attention and research on project management covering many domains, especially information technology (Söderlund, 2004); few researchers have specifically addressed the impact of project management leadership and people management competencies on project delivery success in the rail industry.

Crawford (2005) and also Thamhain and Wlemon (1977) contend that an important issue when considering project management competence or effectiveness is the nature of the projects and the context within which they are conducted. Projects do not occur in a vacuum, they are undertaken in an organisation, thus an organisation's culture, external environment, size, structure as well as project management maturity level can influence the project or project management process.

Therefore, there is a need for further research into the leadership competencies and soft skills of project managers that are required for success in the rail industry. By revealing the extent to which project managers' leadership skills and people management behaviours influence project outcomes, the possibility of providing a framework for ensuring more targeted development and training activities for project managers in the future is presented.

Participants in many of the studies reviewed included mainly project managers. This exploratory study is undertaken by conducting a survey and semi-structured interviews of a cross-section of project professionals in the rail industry.

2:9 Conclusion of Literature Review

From the literature review, we understand that project management success is a subset of project success. Project success theories now include internal metrics which relate to the implementation of the project (project management process) and external metrics which include client and stakeholder satisfaction and financial benefits (project outputs/outcomes).

The competence of project managers is increasingly under scrutiny as the competency of project management personnel is considered to be critical to project performance, and ultimately critical to organisational performance (Crawford, 2005).

Figure 4: Relationship between project management competence and organisational performance

Source: Crawford, (2005)

Following their review of the project management literature on critical success factors, Turner and Muller (2005), concluded that the project management literature seldom identifies the role of project manager leadership style or his competency as a project success factor.

Critical analysis of the theoretical and empirical project management literature led to the discovery of gaps in literature about the role of project management leadership style on project success within the rail industry. Consequently, the primary research will seek to identify project management competencies that have potentially far-reaching implications for project management practice in the rail infrastructure industry.

Chapter Three describes the research methodology and data collection instruments used to gather primary data from a cross-section of project professionals as well as the research design, sample population, validity and reliability and ethical considerations.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3:1 Introduction

This chapter presents a discussion on how the approach to conducting primary research was determined. The main objective of the primary research is to establish whether project managers' competencies has an impact on project outcomes; and identify the project management competencies that lead to successful implementation of complex, large-scale infrastructure projects by exploring the experiences of those involved in delivering complex rail projects.

Secondary research carried out in the literature review indentified the project manager as a critical project success factor according to various authors. However, the literature is not conclusive on the impact of project manager leadership competencies on project outcomes or indeed rail infrastructure projects (Turner and Muller, 2005); more information could only be obtained through primary research.

3:2 Primary Research Methodology

In selecting a research methodology, both the nature of the study and the aims and objectives of the research were considered.

Ekanem (2007) suggests that the selection of the research methodology should be essentially based on the research question under investigation. In undertaking the primary research, both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies were considered.

Creswell (2003) summarised the alternative methods of inquiry in the table below:

Table 4: Quantitative, Qualitative and Mixed Methods Procedures

Quantitative Research Methods	Research Methods	Qualitative Research Methods	Research Methods	Mixed Methods Research Methods
Predetermined instrument based questions		Merging methods, open-ended questions		Both predetermined and emerging methods
Performance data, attitude data, observational data and consensus data		Interview data, observation data, document data and audiovisual data		Both open-ended and closed-ended questions Multiple forms of data drawing on all possibilities
Statistical analysis		Text and image analysis		Statistical and text analysis

Adapted from Creswell, (2003)

Quantitative research methods aim to test hypotheses. Whereas, qualitative data refers to the understanding of participants' perceptions and values which is analysed conceptually (Ekanem, 2007). Southern et al. (2012) assert that quantitative research is suitable for demonstrating causality and being able to generalise, whilst qualitative research methods emphasise situational context. According to Saunders et al (2009), quantitative data is mainly based on meaning that is drawn from numbers with statistical analysis. Gephart (2004) suggests that "*qualitative research often studies phenomena in the environment in which they naturally occur and uses social actors' meanings to understand the phenomena*".

Cohen et al (2007) and Denscombe (2010) illustrate in the table below the main differences between qualitative and quantitative research methods:

Table 5: Differences between Qualitative and Quantitative Research Methods

	Quantitative	Qualitative
Main elements	Numbers, formulas, calculations	Words, feelings, emotions, sounds, vision
Approach	Mainly deductive	Tend to be inductive
Measures	Standard measures exist	Individual measures are created taking into account unique aspects of the study
Procedures	Research procedures tend to be standard and can be replicated for other studies	Research procedures are unique for each study and usually can not be replicated
Presentation	Tables, graphs, charts, and statistics are often used	Presentations tend to be in the form of texts
Relevant data collection methods	Survey	Interviews, focus groups
Size of the sample	Usually large samples	Tend to be small

Adapted from: www.research-methodology.net

Qualitative methods provide the opportunity to gain a deeper understanding of complex phenomena from the perspectives of those experiencing it (Shah and Corley, 2006; Gephart, 2004). But key shortcomings related to qualitative research are identified as time consuming in terms of data collection and analysis as well as the relative small size of the sample compared to quantitative research. Southern et al (2012) also criticise qualitative research methods for being subjective, lacking transparency and making it difficult to generalise from.

According to Neuman (2003), research of social phenomena such as leadership can be undertaken using quantitative, qualitative or combined methods. Shah and Corley (2006) suggest that there many contexts in which quantitative and qualitative empirical methods can be used in combination and encourage the use of both methods jointly to fully understand the phenomenon under study.

The primary research study was undertaken using mixed methods. In selecting this approach, the researcher considered both the research objective and strengths and weaknesses of the different methods. Since the study sought to understand a complex and multi-faceted phenomenon within the context of a particular industry, the mixed methods was considered appropriate in order to overcome some of the limitations of qualitative research such as lack of objectivity and achieve meaningful results and reach significant conclusions.

3:3 Research Questions

The following are the main research questions that framed the study:

- What do you consider to be the most important competencies for effective project managers?
- In what ways are project managers' competencies especially leadership competence critical to project success?
- What are the other key factors that contribute to the successful implementation of rail infrastructure projects?
- How can your organisation ensure that project managers have the relevant competencies to successfully deliver projects?

3:4 Research Instruments

Several data collection methods were considered for this study. These include: structured interviews, semi-structured interviews, focus groups interviews and questionnaires. Focus groups interviews would result in a huge amount of data which would take too long to analyse within the time frame available for preparation of this dissertation. Similarly, observation was ruled out, as it was not possible to have extended periods of contact with the participants within the time-frame of the study.

Whilst structured interview could have been used to measure leadership and project outcomes, this research sought to gain a better understanding of the phenomenon of project management leadership competencies. Questionnaires and a semi-structured interview format were selected based on the type of information sought from participants.

The exploratory research study consisted of an online questionnaire distributed to the target population made up of one hundred project professionals and follow-up semi-structured interviews were conducted with five participants to provide clarification and further insights.

3:5 Pilot Study

The researcher conducted a pilot study to test the validity and reliability of the survey instruments. The pilot study provided the opportunity to clarify and determine whether the interview questions were interpreted the way the researcher intended. From the participants' responses it appeared that the clarity of the questions did not present any problems to them, however, there were some incidence of repetition of questions. The interview guide was therefore modified to ensure better clarity based on feedback from the pilot study.

The pilot study enabled refinement of the interview guide following feedback from the participants. The pilot study consisted of semi-structured interviews with five participants. Experience from the pilot study indicated that validity and reliability of findings can be increased by using data triangulation; hence an online questionnaire was distributed as part of the present study.

3:6 Population and Sample Size

Non-random, purposive and snowball sampling based on professional contact was used to select a sample of 100 participants. The researcher began by identifying a number of project professionals, each professional was asked to identify other potential candidates who had worked on the same project and may be interested in participating in the study. The online questionnaire was then distributed to 100 participants. 47 people responded, which equates to a 47% response rate. All the study participants were employed in London, UK.

The population of the study were project professionals working on a complex large-scale signalling upgrade programme in TfL's Capital Programmes Directorate. In order to avoid functional discipline or job type bias, the sample included individuals from all disciplines, including Project Sponsors, Project Managers, Planners, Engineers, Commercial Managers, Risk Managers and End-User Representatives.

Purposive sampling was used to select 5 candidates for follow-up, face to face semi-structured interviews to discuss significant findings from the online questionnaire.

Participation in the study was voluntary and anonymous. All potential participants were sent an email describing the subject of the research and requesting their consent prior to the interview - Appendix A. Participants were also advised in the email that their participation was voluntary and anonymous.

3:7 Data Collection Procedures and Analysis Method

The exploratory mixed method study relied on questionnaires and semi-structured interviews for data collection.

Questionnaires

Using the secondary research in Chapter 2 as a framework, a questionnaire was developed by the researcher with questions categorised into themes corresponding to the competencies based on a review of project managers' job descriptions as advertised on the internet for project management roles in the rail industry and competencies identified as the most important for effective project leadership in large projects, high uncertainty projects and very novel projects in Krahn and Hartment's (2006).

An online questionnaire was selected due to the simplicity and speed of administering it and gaining feedback from participants. In an environment where most of the participants are office based, the online survey provided an accessible and convenient method of data collection.

The questionnaire was electronically distributed to the target population via an email detailing the background to the study. Participants were assured that their responses would be anonymous and confidential. The questionnaire and cover letter was sent via email to the participants on 2 April, 2013 and closed on 15 April, 2013.

The questionnaire was structured into four sections: Section One asked questions regarding participants' background and demographics. Section Two used Likert scaled questions that sought to identify the project management competencies that contributed to project success. Section Three was focused on identifying the top five competencies for successful projects. Section Four sought to identify project success factors for rail infrastructure projects. A four-point Likert scale was used to assess perceived importance of the factors: Not Important (1), Slightly Important (2), Quite Important (3) and Very Important (4). The full questionnaire is included as Appendix B.

The questionnaire acted as a precursor for the semi-structured interviews, drawing out themes from participants, which would be explored further at the interview stage with a smaller sample.

Semi-structured Interviews

As noted by Bowling (2005), questionnaires do not provide the opportunity for the researcher to probe respondents and ask more questions. Semi-structured interviews were therefore conducted with five participants to provide clarification and further insights into their perceptions regarding the importance of project management competencies that lead to successful implementation of large-scale rail infrastructure projects.

Following feedback of the online questionnaire, a purposive sampling technique was used to select five interview candidates, from the pool of questionnaire respondents. The number of interview participants was limited to five due to resource and time constraints. The selection process for the interviews was centred on targeting respondents with considerable project experience.

Interviews were scheduled at the convenience of the participants during the last week in April 2013 at their preferred location. Participants were required to sign the Informed Consent form shown in Appendix A prior to participating in the interviews.

To protect the identity and confidentiality of the participants, each of them was assigned an alphanumeric code number ranging from D01- D05 and their names did not appear anywhere in the data.

Semi-structured interviews took place using interview techniques as proposed by Rubin and Rubin (2005). The semi-structured interview consisted of open and closed questions; the open questions provided the participants with some flexibility when responding to questions and allowed the process to be guided by the responses of the participants. Although the interview questions were prepared in advance, they were used only as a guide to the interviewer, in some instances additional probing questions were asked to dig deeper and explore emerging themes and draw out further insights from the participants.

A sample of the interview guide is included at Appendix C.

The interview protocol included the use of audio recording procedures and an interview guide to facilitate the sessions which lasted approximately 45-60 minutes each. The researcher used an audio tape recording device during the interview as the primary means of collecting data during the interviews as well as hand written notes.

To ensure accuracy and confidentiality, the researcher personally transcribed the recorded interviews within 24 hours of each interview and emailed typed up notes to the participants for their review. The participants were requested to verify the transcripts and confirm by email or telephone the accuracy of the transcription. The average feedback time was 24-48 hours as all participants were willing to accommodate the researcher's timescales.

The notes from the interviews remain in the possession of the researcher and are locked away in a safe place and will be destroyed once the assessment and evaluation process is completed.

Interview data was coded with a view of identifying common patterns and ideas from participants' responses as well as generating themes and sub-themes from the research. Saunders et al. (2009) argue that in qualitative research, there is no universally accepted coding system. Therefore, the researcher adopted a manual coding system to identify key themes and sub-themes from the research.

The study data was collected on an ongoing basis and organised through an inductive process of recording, tabulation in excel, coding, and analysing until meaningful ideas emerged. The data was subsequently analysed using a thematic approach to identify patterns and draw out themes that emerged from the interview.

No preliminary hypothesis was offered to the respondents and data was continuously analysed to identify common themes. Manual line by line analysis of the interview data was conducted. Key words and preliminary themes and sub-themes were noted next to each point in the transcript and subsequently grouped together according to emerging key themes. In order to facilitate this process, the data was organised into a checklist matrix to provide a visual display.

The process of coding the data required a comparative reflection on project manager competencies and behaviour noted during the secondary research. Therefore, the coding system used the existing literature on the most important project management skills and competencies to assist in determining key findings.

Audit of Project Manager Job Profile

As part of the primary research, the researcher also conducted a review of project managers' job descriptions and profiles in the rail industry, in order to identify the behavioural and technical competencies that are currently deemed as essential or required to perform the role of a project

manager in the industry. These competencies were subsequently included as part of the study questionnaire.

3:8 Validity and Reliability

Saunders et al. (2009) advocate that validity and reliability are dimensions that should be considered in any research from the design stage to data collection and analysis.

According to Neuman (2003), the validity implies the authenticity of the study to be a fair and objective assessment of the social phenomenon through the perceptions of the participants. Creswell (2003) explains that instrument reliability is equivalent to a research tool or survey's capacity to measure and produce repeatable results.

Validity and reliability was strengthened in this primary research through the use of a number of strategies.

Firstly, the research instruments underwent a field test via pilot study which led to its refinement.

Secondly, the audio tapes of the interviews provided an effective reference point to the original source to verify any potential discrepancies. Also, interviews were transcribed word for word by the researcher within 24 hours of each interview and transcripts reviewed by the participants. Reliability was assured by appropriate data analysis using coding techniques to organise data into themes and sub-themes.

Furthermore, the mixed methods of data collection enabled triangulation of findings. Saunders et al. (2009) explain that triangulation refers to the use of different data collection techniques within one study in order to ensure "*the data are telling you what you think they are telling you*". Creswell (2003) argues that triangulation helps to minimise systematic biases and validate research findings.

The multiple sources of evidence for this study came from the survey, semi-structured interviews and document review. Narratives and detailed descriptions of participants' experiences are also included

in the report to maximise accuracy and to minimise possible distortion resulting from the researcher's bias.

3:9 Ethical Considerations

According to Saunders et al. (2009), research ethics are concerned with the moral responsibilities associated with the research topic and design, as well as the way the data is collected, analysed and processed. Saunders et al. (2009) argue that it is essential for the researcher to consider research ethics as they may have significant impact on access to individuals and organisations as a whole to obtain the data under investigation.

Consequently, the researcher complied with the University of Durham's "Policy for the Maintenance of Good Practice in Research". Furthermore, prior to undertaking primary research, the researcher ensured that the purpose and nature of the study was explained to participants and they were encouraged to ask questions or seek clarification. Informed consent of the study participants was obtained in order to assure the transparency of the research and highlight voluntary participation of the participants.

Participants' confidentiality and anonymity was guaranteed throughout the entire process. Participants were reassured that they could withdraw from the study at any time without penalty. The participants were assured of data confidentiality and that no sensitive information such as their names would be included in the study and that no harm would occur to them as a result of participating in the study. All participants gave their consent to be interviewed by signing and returning the informed consent form to the researcher prior to the interviews.

Paper transcripts were locked away in safe place and will be destroyed once the results of this module are released. Data stored electronically are password protected and will also be deleted at the end of the assessment process.

3:10 Summary

In this chapter, the research design chosen for the study was identified as mixed method combining qualitative and quantitative methods of data collection. 100 project professionals in a public sector rail organisation were selected to participate in the study. A non-random purposive sampling technique was used to select the participants. Questionnaires and face to face in-depth semi-structured interviews were the data collection instruments.

Chapter 4 presents results and analysis of the findings; the conclusions and recommendations are presented in Chapter 5.

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS

4:1 Overview

Results of the primary research and discussion of the key findings in relation to the research questions are presented in this chapter.

The research focused on the impact of project managers' competencies on major infrastructure project by exploring the experiences of those involved in delivering complex rail projects.

Project success and project success criteria were discussed at length in the literature review in Chapter Two. A project is considered an overall success if the project meets the technical performance specification (including safety) and/or mission to be performed, and if there is a high level of satisfaction concerning the project outcome among key people in the parent organization, key people in the project team and key users or clientele of the project effort (Baker et al (1983).

According to Allport et al (2008) the factors contributing to project success are complex and often context-dependent, no simple set of best practices is likely to exist for any industry. But some factors are essential and some important. This study seeks to reveal what these are for the rail industry.

The study produced a number of significant findings, which are discussed in detail below.

4:2 Questionnaire Results and Analysis

The questionnaire (Appendix B) was structured into four sections namely: Section One – Demographic questions, Section Two – Project Management Competencies, Section Three - Top Five Competencies for Successful Projects and Section Four – Project Success Factors.

The questionnaire was instrumental in assessing the demographics of the participants as well as discerning emerging themes and patterns from the research. Data from questionnaire responses was downloaded into Microsoft Excel to enable analysis.

Session One – Participants’ Demographics

The demographic questions were designed to obtain information from respondents in some general areas: the gender and age of respondents, the respondents’ work and project experience, their role in project management and the average complexity of previous projects they had been involved in.

The researcher received 47 fully completed responses to the survey from a sample of 100 project professionals from Transport for London (TfL) and Bombardier Transportation UK (BTUK) giving a response rate of 47%. The researcher found that the proactive pre-survey and follow-up communications were fundamental to the high response rate.

Analysis of the demographics showed that the vast majority of study participants were project professionals experienced in complex rail projects, which is the focus of the dissertation.

The highest proportion of participants were Engineers who formed 43%, closely followed by Project Managers who formed 34%. The lowest group was made up of “Other” category which included Risk Managers, Project Sponsor and User Acceptance Representatives.

Functional Area	Frequency	Percentage %
Project Management	16	34%
Engineering	20	43%
Planning	6	13%
Commercial	1	2%
Other	4	8%
Total	47	100%

Table 6: Breakdown of Questionnaire Participants’ Demographics by discipline

Figure 5: Figure showing Participants' discipline

Two thirds of participants were male and one third female which was not surprising, given that the rail industry is male dominated in the UK.

Gender	Frequency	Percentage %
Male	32	68%
Female	15	32%
	47	100%

Table 7: Breakdown of Questionnaire Participants' Demographics by Gender

The majority of study participants had at least a bachelor's degree, 34% of participants were educated to bachelor's degree and masters' degree levels – representing 68% cumulatively. While, 6% and 26% had a doctorate or NVQs and GCSEs respectively.

Highest Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage %
Doctorate Degree	3	6%
Masters Degree	16	34%
Bachelors Degree	16	34%
NVQ/GCSE's	12	26%
	47	100%

Table 8: Breakdown of Questionnaire Participants' Demographics by education

An overwhelming majority (91%) of respondents rated the average complexity of previous projects they had been involved as highly complex. The measure of project complexity was subjective, due to each individual's own assessment. However, factors that might have been taken into consideration include: number of organisations and stakeholders involved, budget and timeline for project delivery, number of communication routes, number of functions, technology and interface with other systems.

Figure 6: Breakdown of Questionnaire Response on Average Project Complexity

Furthermore, 75% of participants reported having at least 5 years project environment experience and 53% were in projects with over 60 project team members. 92% of participants had worked in projects whose value exceeded £5,000,000.00. Figures 7, 8 and 9 provide the visual representation of the distribution.

Figure 7: Distribution of Questionnaire Response on Project Experience

Figure 8: Distribution of Questionnaire Response on Average Project Team Size

Figure 9: Distribution of Questionnaire Response on Average Monetary Value

The above demographics indicate that majority of respondents were fairly experienced in large-scale projects. A full breakdown of the demographic statistics is shown in Appendix D.

4:3 Project Management Competencies

The questionnaire was designed to examine which project management competencies were deemed most important by participants when it comes to the successful implementation of complex rail projects. As well as to gauge the general perceptions of participants on specific factors which they perceived as critical to project success as defined in this study.

Session 2 of the survey instrument addressed Research Question 1 by asking questions regarding the most important competencies for effective project managers. Session 3 asked participants to select and rank the top 5 most important project managers' competencies in the rail industry respectively. Each competence was assessed on four-point Likert scale: very important (4), quite important (3), slightly important (2) and not important (1).

The competencies were selected from project managers' job descriptions as advertised on the internet for project management roles in the rail industry and competencies identified as the most important for effective project leadership in large projects, high uncertainty projects and very novel projects in Krahn and Hartment's (2006).

An exploratory data analysis approach was undertaken to derive meaning from the primary data generated from the survey rather than descriptive statistics. Microsoft Excel was used to organise and categorise findings into different themes to enable subsequent analysis. The results were then analysed by means of percentages and shown diagrammatically rather than mean values that quantitative research would provide.

Results are presented in table 9 below:

Table 9: Results of Section Two of Survey Questionnaire

Question No.	Project Management Competencies/Behaviours	Not Important %	Slightly Important %	Quite Important %	Very Important %
12	Ability to develop clear project scope and manage the expectation of the business and stakeholders	0.0	0.0	0.0	100.0
13	Ability to build and set out a clear project vision of what is to be accomplished with project team members' cooperation and support	0.0	19.1	27.7	53.2
14	Good financial management/budgeting skills, and a good understanding of financial control and procurement processes.	0.0	17.0	53.2	29.8
15	Ability to understand the core technology of the project deliverables	0.0	23.4	38.3	38.3
16	Ability to effectively communicate project priorities, which align with the project goals and company objectives/values	0.0	21.3	27.7	51.1
17	Ability to manage/lead and motivate multidisciplinary teams to deliver effective performance	0.0	17.0	27.7	55.3
18	Ability to manage change	0.0	19.1	38.3	42.6
19	Broad knowledge and understanding of commercial and contract issues in a technology and transport service environment	0.0	31.9	42.6	25.5
20	Ability to remove obstacles and resolve conflicts	0.0	17.0	36.2	46.8
21	Ability to complete cost estimates and produce project budget to support planning and decision-making	0.0	27.7	44.7	27.7

Question No.	Project Management Competencies/Behaviours	Not Important	Slightly Important	Quite Important	Very Important
22	Ability to effectively delegate tasks and empower others to make important decisions	0.0	0.0	48.9	51.1
23	Exceptional organisational skills and the ability to manage multiple and conflicting priorities and make sound decisions in a high pressure environment	0.0	19.1	38.3	42.6
24	Adopts a leadership style appropriate to the specific team and work situation	0.0	23.4	44.7	31.9
25	Accepts total accountability, even when tasks are delegated	0.0	23.4	38.3	38.3
26	Delivers on what was agreed to the required quality, on time and within budget	0.0	17.0	44.7	38.3
27	Ability to identify resource requirements needed to support planning and decision-making	0.0	29.8	31.9	38.3
28	Ability to effectively use project planning & control techniques to develop schedules and manage risks	0.0	27.7	42.6	29.8
29	Ability to build strong working relationships with colleagues, clients and service providers	0.0	0.0	48.9	51.1
30	A positive attitude and ability to deliver cost effective solutions when met with difficult and challenging project impacting risks and issues	12.8	14.9	38.3	34.0
31	Ability to effectively present to senior management	12.8	17.0	40.4	29.8
32	Ability to influence people at all levels across the organisation and outside, including negotiating and successfully facilitating joint decision making	0.0	19.1	36.2	44.7
33	Ability to manage projects and conflicting priorities to achieve tight	0.0	17.0	40.4	42.6

Question No.	Project Management Competencies/Behaviours	Not Important	Slightly Important	Quite Important	Very Important
	deadlines				
34	Domain knowledge in the area of capital project management	14.9	25.5	36.2	23.4
35	Ability to motivate and inspire project team members to perform better	0.0	19.1	36.2	44.7
36	Professional qualification in Project or Programme Management, eg. APM, Prince 2 or MSP	31.9	25.5	23.4	19.1
37	Ability to identify, evaluate, prioritise and manage risks (Safety, Commercial and potentially Environmental)	0.0	19.1	42.6	38.3
	Not Listed				
	Document Management				
	Understanding and managing people impacts of project				
	Openness & Honesty, ability to face facts				
	Listen to End User and actively involve them throughout project lifecycle				

The key themes and overall patterns emerging from the researcher's analysis of survey results are discussed below.

As show in Table 9 above, the only question which all participants unanimously agreed on was question 12 - the importance of the ability to develop clear project scope and manage the expectation of the business and stakeholders. All participants ranked this competence as very important to the successful implementation of rail projects.

Question 12	Participants (%)
Ability to develop clear project scope and manage the expectation of the business and stakeholders	
Not Important	0
Slightly Important	0
Quite Important	0
Very Important	100%

Table 10: Results of answers to Question 12 of Survey

Conversely, 31.1% of participants concluded that formal professional qualification in project or programme management, such as APM and PRINCE2 was not important, whilst 25.5% stated it was slightly important, 23.3% thought it was quite important and only 19.1% thought it was a very important competence in delivering successful rail projects. Therefore more than half of participants (57.4%) concluded that a formal project management qualification was not an essential competence for a project manager to have to successfully manage or implement complex rail projects.

Question 36	Participants (%)
Professional qualification in Project or Programme Management, eg. APM, Prince 2 or MSP	
Not Important	31.9%
Slightly Important	25.5%
Quite Important	23.4%
Very Important	19.1%

Table 11: Results of answers to Question 36 of Survey

Comparison of the lowest (professional qualification- Q. 36) and highest (ability to develop clear project scope – Q. 12) scored competencies are shown in figure 10 below.

Figure 10: Comparison of Results to Questions 12 and 36 of Survey

Another point to note from the survey results in Table 9 above, was that the leadership and people management skills were ranked as either quite important or very important by majority of participants. For example, Questions 16, 17, 22 and 29 relating to communication, leadership and people management skills, at least 50% of respondents thought that those skills were “very important” and 27.7%, 27.7%, 48.9 and 48.9% respectively thought they “quite important”.

In contrast, for the technical project management competencies in Questions 14, 19, 21 and 28 which are around Project Management Institute’s (PMI) knowledge areas, relating to project management domains such as Scope management, Time management (Q. 28 &), Cost management (Q.14 & 21) and Risk management (Q. 19); less than 30% of participants considered these technical competencies as “very important”. This is consistent with Schlick’s (1988) view that technical knowledge is not as important as people skills for project success. Details of a comparison of the above results are shown in table 12. Questions 16, 17, 22, and 29 relate to leadership or people skills, whilst Questions 21, 19, 28 and 14 relate to technical skills as discussed above.

	Question 16	Question 17	Question 22	Question 29	Question 21	Question 19	Question 28	Question 14
Not Important	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Slightly Important	21.3	17	0	0	27.7	31.9	27.7	17
Quite Important	27.7	27.7	48.9	48.9	44.7	42.6	42.6	53.2
Very Important	51.1	55.3	51.1	51.1	27.7	25.5	29.8	29.8

Table 12: Results to Questions 14, 16, 17, 19, 21, 22, 28 & 29 of Survey

The participants’ responses with regards to technical competencies may be due to the fact that their organisations have experts in these fields specifically employed to manage risk, cost/contract, planning, etc as indicated in the role descriptions under demographic questions. Therefore, their organisations have Cost Managers, Commercial Managers, Risk Managers and Planners overseeing their respective areas. Hence, project managers need not be particularly competent in these technical aspects of project management. As one participant noted,

“Although technical competencies are very important to a project’s success, a large and complex project will often allow specialists (commercial, planning, risk management, technical experts) to be employed. This means that the role of the project manager is more focused on leading the team and removing obstacles to achieving the project aims”.

Other competencies stated by the participants which were not originally included in the list of competencies by the researcher include:

- Openness and honesty with an ability to face facts
- Understanding and managing people impacts of projects
- Document management
- Ability to listen to end users and actively involve them throughout the project lifecycle.

Competencies “Not Listed” by Researcher

Document Management

Document and data management is fundamental to having accurate current information in all forms especially drawings and contracts, scope and work descriptions.

Understanding and managing people impacts of project

Both from within the project construction team and beyond. For example, customer and station management level, or as part of planned closures, The effect of the Crossrail development at Tottenham Court Road is a real nuisance to users, pedestrians, local retailers and other businesses and was definitely considered before construction began.

Similarly, when the Jubilee line was extended to Stratford many years ago there was a lot of business relocation through compulsory purchase orders in preparation for the work. During construction when the new interchange and lines at Westminster were developed there were stories of the effect on Big Ben (St Stephen’s Tower, more accurately) of construction of a tunnel under/near it.

Project managers should be able to manage these people impact of projects effectively.

Competencies “Not Listed” by Researcher
<p>Openness & Honesty, ability to face facts</p> <p>Project managers’ ability to present facts, reflecting the need to say if the project is running late or when an unforeseen issue arises.</p>
<p>Listen to End User and actively involve them throughout project lifecycle</p> <p>This was explained by the respondents “<i>as the ability not to guess what Operations want and need, but the drive to go and ask and involve them..., second guessing or moving forward from an incorrect or ill informed view is not desirable</i>”.</p>

Table 13: Competencies “Not Listed” by Researcher

4:4 Top 5 Project Managers’ competencies

Session 3 of the survey instrument was analysed for frequencies in order to compare the ranking of top five rankings of selected competencies. Interestingly, the statistical analysis of the survey data indicates that a significant number of participants (40%, 19 of 47 respondents) ranked leadership as the no.1 most important project management competence. This was closely followed by the ability to motivate and lead direct reports and project teams which was ranked by 26% (12 participants) as either the top or second most important project management competence. The other competencies that make the “top 5 competencies” shown in Table 15 below include: good knowledge of the core technology of the engineering solution, stakeholder management and relevant prior experience.

TOP 5 COMPETENCIES
Leadership
Ability to motivate and lead direct reports and project teams
Good knowledge of the core technology of the engineering solution
Stakeholder management
Relevant prior experience

Table 14: Top 5 Competencies

4:5 Key Success Factors

Session 4 addressed Research Question 3 – “what are the other key factors that contribute to the successful implementation of rail infrastructure projects?”

The top three success factors (see Table 15 below) with at least 50% of participants indicating that the factor was very important are: skilled team members (55.3%), effective decision making and issue resolution (53.5%) and project managers’ leadership skills (51.1%). The findings in this session are consistent with findings from the earlier two sessions which also indicated that soft people skills such as leadership was motivating project team members, stakeholder management and effective communications and decision making are regarded as very important to project success by the study participants. Other factors mentioned by respondents which were not listed by the researcher are: “*safety awareness*” and “*listen first, take advice, then implement*”.

Top 3 Success Factors	Not Important	Slightly Important	Quite Important	Very Important
	%	%	%	%
Skilled project team members	0.0	0.0	44.7	55.3
Effective decision-making and issue resolution	0.0	17.0	29.8	53.2
Project managers’ leadership skills (vision and motivating others)	0.0	17.0	31.9	51.1

Table 15: Top 3 Success Factors

Appendix E contains details of results from this session of the Questionnaire responses.

4:6 Survey Themes

The key emerging themes from the questionnaires comments and feedback are reflected in the figure below:

Figure 11: Emerging Themes from Questionnaire Responses on the Competencies for Successful Project Management in the Rail Industry

What emerged from the questionnaire results was that no single factor or competence will, in isolation, influence project success. However, analyses of the results of all three sessions of the survey responses indicate that the above competencies or factors highlighted are very important to successful implementation of rail projects.

4:7 Interview Results and Analysis

Having elicited the key findings from the survey responses on the most important project management competencies and project success factors, the researcher used the subsequent interviews to further explore the emerging themes from the questionnaire, to get a rich set of data and to answer the research questions.

Three project managers and two engineers from the survey respondents were selected for follow-up semi-structured interviews because of their experience and knowledge in rail infrastructure projects. The intent of the follow-up interviews was to provide clarification and further insights to the aspects explored via the questionnaire and answer the research questions.

4:8 Project Success

Project Management Institute (2008) defines project success as the extent to which the project meets specific objectives within the constraints of resources, time, performance objectives or scope as defined by the project stakeholders and the degree of customer satisfaction. All the interviewees agreed that this was an appropriate definition of project success within the rail industry. Interestingly, one interviewee whilst agreeing with PMI's definition said they felt that their organisation regarded completing projects within budget and on time as the most important success criteria without necessarily checking that the scope agreed at the beginning is delivered at the end.

However in addition, two interviewees stressed the importance of benefits realisation and ensuring end user satisfaction with the project output by having a "feedback loop" throughout the project lifecycle. One participant stated that the customers or end users should be central to project success, saying that, "*project success should start with the customers and not be tagged on at the end as an afterthought*". This emphasis on customer satisfaction echoes the conclusions reached by De Wit (1988) and Munns & Bjeirmi (1996), who found that stakeholder satisfaction was key to project success.

One interviewee referred to safety metrics in their definition of project success.

4:9 Project Management Competencies and Project Success

To address research question 1 and 2, the interviewer asked candidates which competencies they considered to be the most important for effective project managers and the reasons for their selection.

Similar to the findings from the survey, the interview results indicate that the most important project management competencies were the “soft people” skills. Interviewees mentioned leadership and communication skills – especially the ability to listen as the most important competency. Themes that emerged from the interview are shown in the table below:

Interview Question 2: What do you consider to be the most important competencies for effective project managers?	Frequency	Percent
Leadership – including having visions and goals	5	100%
Communication skills - including the ability to listen	5	100%
People management and team building skills	3	60%
Planning	3	60%
Self confidence – including courage to manage powerful stakeholders	3	60%
Decision making and issue resolution	2	40%
Technical engineering knowledge	2	40%
Decision making and issue resolution	1	20%
Negotiation and influencing skills	1	20%
Adaptability and creativity in solving complex problems	1	20%
Prior relevant experience	1	20%

Table 16: Responses to Interview Question 2

Leadership, communication, planning, self confidence and team building skills were ranked very highly in the interview. According to participants, it is very important to work out a communications strategy from the very beginning due to the diverse and powerful nature of the stakeholders. The ability to listen was emphasised by the two engineers interviewed. They said that project managers must be able to listen effectively to the experts within their project teams in making decisions.

These results support Posner's (1987) findings; who found in his research into what makes a good project manager found that communication, organisational, leadership, team building and coping skills were ranked above technological skills by participants at a project management seminar.

Similarly, El-Sabaa's (2001) in his study into the skills of an effective project manager in information systems projects, electricity projects, and agricultural projects, also found that soft people skills of project managers have the most significant influence on project management practices.

Ability to effectively plan how the project will be delivered was another factor that was highlighted by interviewees. As one interviewee puts it "*without appropriate planning, the project is bound to fail*".

With regards to role of project management competencies on project success, the interviewees whilst acknowledging that project managers' competencies are important to success; state that the combined competencies of the project team are more important. The view was that having the right project team members with the right knowledge and expertise in their relevant fields is crucial to success. This interview finding directly correlates to questionnaire findings, where 100% of the survey respondents stated that skilled team members was either very important (55.3%) or quite important (44.7%).

4:10 Project Manager Leadership Attributes and Project Success

As shown in Table 12 above, all interviewees stated that leadership is critical to project success. Interviewees stated that leadership has to do with "*having vision and goals*", "*leading by example*", "*leading from the front*", "*self confidence*" and "*providing a nurturing or enabling environment*". One participant stated that project manager leadership skill is critical as the project manager is the person who "*brings everything together*".

Another participant thought project manager leadership skill was important because, "*project manager behaviour impacts everybody in the team including the contractor or supplier*". The view was that

project manager's behaviour drives other stakeholders' behaviour especially project team members and suppliers and inappropriate behaviour could lead to commercial issues resulting to claims and counter claims between client and supplier/s.

With further probing, interviewees further stated that leadership is essential to projects success in the rail infrastructure projects especially complex rail projects because of the large size and diverse nature of the project teams. Project managers have limited choice in the formation of project teams and therefore have to work with and motivate culturally diverse teams and people, who they may not necessarily have chosen themselves. A competent project leader is therefore required to bring out the best from people with a diverse range of skills set and background.

Interviewees also explained that rail projects often involve powerful and diverse stakeholders who are required to be brought together and sometimes gain agreement from in order to move forward. Leadership skills, they say are necessary to effectively manage these "*powerful stakeholders*". Furthermore, one interviewee suggested that project manager leadership is required to "*foster a collaborative relationship between client and contractor*" and within the project team itself.

Another, interesting finding from one interview was that different leadership skills are required during the different phases of the project lifecycle. Whilst transformational or visionary leadership is required during the early stages of the project, transactional leadership is required towards the end of the project and to ensure effective close out and handover of the project to operations and maintenance. The interviewee felt that project managers need to adapt his or her style to the situation as required.

A limited number of empirical studies have found a modest link between project performance and project management leadership competence (Turner & Muller, 2005). But this study found significant evidence that suggest that the leadership skill of project managers has a vital role to play in project performance and success in complex rail infrastructure projects.

Results of the secondary research, pilot study, survey and interviews undertaken in the course of this study, support the notion that leadership as well as other “soft people” skills such as communication (including listening skills) and prior relevant experience are crucial to project outcomes.

Separating or measuring the specific effects of project management leadership on project success maybe difficult and was not the focus of this study. However, this does not negate the findings that project management leadership and people skills are important and should not be dismissed.

4:11 Other Project Success Factors in the Rail Industry

To address research question 3, the interviewer asked participants what other key factors contribute to the successful implementation of rail infrastructure projects. Table 17 reflects in no particular order, the factors that interviewees considered to be key project success factors within complex rail infrastructure environment.

Interview Question 5: What are the key factors that contribute to the successful implementation of rail infrastructure projects?	
Organisational culture	Stakeholder involvement throughout project lifecycle
Competent Project team	Senior management support to the project
Right project scope and requirements from the outset	Collocation of client project team and supplier project team
Planning	Understanding access requirements to the railway
Right contractual framework and right supplier	Ensure quality work to avoid the need for rework
Awareness of Safety	Effective change control

Table 17: Responses to Interview Question 5

Results from this question indicate that the interviewees considered success factors from the perspective of the project management team and the factors that impact their ability to effectively deliver the project objectives or goals. Unlike Allport et al. (2008) for example, who in their analysis of 22 case studies of rail infrastructure projects across several countries, looked at project success from

the perspective of the promoter of the project; which in their view was the government or public authority in the each country.

A factor that stood out from interviewees' responses was - competent project team members. This factor was consistently highlighted by study participants. This alludes to the belief that the project manager is not expected to be competent in every aspect of the project, but is expected to rely on skilled and competent team members to deliver project objectives.

Apart from project manager and project team competencies, the research found that the factors that have the biggest impact on project success was having a clear scope and well-defined requirements; planning how the project would be delivered; stakeholder involvement from the beginning of the project and throughout the project lifecycle.

4:12 Project Managers' Leadership Training and Development

None of the interviewees had received formal leadership training. All three project managers interviewed said their leadership skills were developed through "on-the-job" experience and one mentioned other informal methods - reading management literature and coaching. Participants stated that there was no formal leadership training specifically for project managers within their organisation, but leadership training was provided to senior managers.

Finally, the researcher addressed research question 4 by asking participants how their organisation can ensure that project managers have the relevant competencies to successfully deliver complex rail projects.

Participants believe a variety of methods could be used to develop leadership competency of project managers; including shadowing, 360 feedback and management literature being made readily available. It was unanimously agreed that shadowing an experienced project manager and "on-the-job" experience were the most effective methods of developing leadership skills.

However, the danger associated with this, as one interviewee noted, is that bad behaviour or negative leadership styles could easily be copied from the experienced project managers and perpetuated leading to systemic problems for the organisation. The key to this method of developing project managers is shadowing or mentoring by an experienced project manager with the right behaviours.

Interestingly, interviewees thought that formal leadership training and project management professional qualifications like PRINCE 2 or APM have limited value. In their view, leadership cannot be learnt in the classroom. According to them, leadership skills are best developed from giving new project managers small packages of work to deliver which will provide the opportunity for them to build confidence in their abilities.

4:13 Assumptions & Limitations

The study participants are based in the two organisations currently delivering one project – although they have had experience in different projects the findings cannot be generalised across the whole rail industry.

The researcher assumes that participants gave open and honest insights into their experiences. It was also assumed that demographic factors such as age, sex, ethnic and educational background did not influence the participant's answers to the interview questions. But the diverse experiences of the participants would have coloured their responses.

The size of sample population may be considered as small in absolute and relative terms due to the size of the organisation and industry under investigation. Nonetheless, as argued by Crouch and McKenzie (2009), the human-oriented type of qualitative research that focuses on participants' perceptions and values – such as was undertaken by this study, may be used to justify a small sample size.

Furthermore, the diversity of employees presented in the sample provided the opportunity to evaluate a broad range of employees' perceptions regarding the impact of project management competencies on project success and how these competencies can be developed.

Therefore, despite the study limitations, this research holds significant importance as it adds value to the project management literature through gaining a good understanding of the important project management competencies and how they impact project success.

4:14 Summary

Project manager competency has traditionally been viewed as the application of the hard project management methods and tools needed to create a desired product or service (Crawford, 2005). However, these hard knowledge and skills need to be combined with an individual's personality and core character attributes to provide a balanced view of a project manager's level of competence (Morris, 2002). Following their research, Pinto and Kharbanda (1995) also suggest that the problems a project manager will encounter are more behavioural than technical.

The findings of this study provide strong evidence that successful project outcomes can be affected by project managers' competencies especially their leadership, stakeholder management and communication skills which incorporates having vision and goals, leading by example, leading from the front, self confidence, team building and providing a nurturing or enabling environment.

These competencies are reflected in the potential success of the project for the client and operations staff, as their continued engagement as stakeholders in every project would enable greater understanding of project deliverables, perhaps cater for acceptable changes to the project's scope, cater for change in operations to use what is being delivered and make handover easier.

These findings are consistent with the literature reviewed. Other researchers have found that the primary problem of project managers is not technical, but human (Posner, 1987 & El-Sabaa, 2001).

The literature asserts that technical knowledge is not as important as people skills for project success (Schlick, 1988).

The study findings are in consistent with the view that technical project management skills such as risk management, procurement, scheduling and cost management are not as important as the leadership or people management skills. However, the study findings indicate that project managers' engineering knowledge as well as having skilled project team members are just as important to adequately address all aspects of project success in the rail industry.

Project managers are expected to bring together and motivate disparate professionals and experts, develop a cohesive team and deliver complex rail infrastructure projects to time, costs and other performance criteria. The study found that project management leadership has an influence on project outcomes through impact on project team performance by providing vision and motivating skilled project teams.

Competent and highly skilled project managers will lead to better outcomes for their projects and organisations in general. Developing the non-technical skills of project managers will empower project managers to achieve better results or project outcomes.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5:1 Conclusion

The study used a mixed method exploratory research to determine the project management competencies that lead to successful implementation of complex large-scale rail infrastructure projects; with a view that organisations will benefit from this knowledge as they implement major capital projects in rail infrastructure. A secondary consideration was how project managers' leadership competencies can be effectively developed by organisations.

The ability of organisations to successfully implement projects is critical to their ability to meet their strategic objectives, as shown by the growing reliance on project management as a method of organising work (Cooke-Davies & Arzymanow, 2003; Golob, 2002 & Morris & Pinto, 2004).

It is widely accepted among project professionals that there is a need for leadership in the managing of projects. Despite some study in the area of project management leadership, for example Turner & Müller (2005), the extent to which leadership influences project success in complex rail projects is not clear. The objective of this study was to add to the existing body of project management leadership research.

The research conclusions are derived from the totality of the evidence assembled during the primary and secondary research. The following main themes were identified in the study:

- Projects are, by their intrinsic nature, unique endeavours. Consequently, projects, even if similar, will not be implemented or executed in the same way, with the same people or in the same environmental context due to constant change in the external environment.
- As a result, during the execution of a project, there will always be some degree of uncertainty which puts the project outcomes at risk and thus require skilful management. This difficulty is further compounded for large and complex rail infrastructure projects because they usually involve multiple contracts, suppliers and contractors and other third party organisations.

Furthermore, complex large-scale rail projects often have multiple sub-projects and the required co-ordination among sub-projects introduces additional risks and complexity - as delay in one area can have a ripple effects on other areas.

- The study found that project managers with the right blend of leadership skills, communication skills, stakeholder management skills, engineering knowledge and relevant experience are required to effectively manage complex large-scale rail projects. Participants in this study strongly indicated that project managers need to have technical engineering knowledge, leadership and people skills to enable them lead and motivate diverse project professionals effectively and achieve successful project outcomes.
- Scholars of project management tend to agree that whilst the technical aspects or dimension of project management are important, it is the behavioural competencies or soft skills, of project managers that are required for success. The study findings suggest that project outcomes can be affected by project leadership that incorporates the ideals of “*having vision and goals*”, “*leading by example*”, “*leading from the front*”, “*self confidence*” and “*providing a nurturing or enabling environment*”. Project success requires that project managers not only manage projects, but also lead their teams.
- Despite the recognition that leadership is important, project managers whilst trained in the technical aspects of project management, generally lack sufficient leadership training in TfL. As Cooke-Davies & Arzymanow (2003) and other authors note, effective management of the two dimensions – technical dimension and human dimension is required for success.
- The study findings support recent emphasis and focus on so called “soft” project management skills. According to Wideman (2001), in recent times, there has been a definite shift to the “human” side of project management. As project management has incorporated techniques for effectively dealing with people, we can expect there to be a trend towards firmer leadership in projects (Wideman, 2001).
- Whilst acknowledging that project managers’ competencies are key to addressing the human aspects of project work and are therefore relevant, these are not exclusive factors impacting

project performance. The results of this study suggest that a cohesive and highly competent project team is equally important.

- Professional project management qualifications like PRINCE2 or APM were ranked the least important out of 25 factors by study participants. There appears to be disconnect between study findings and the reality of project manager's job profile; since organisations often stress the importance of technical project management skills such as procurement, risk management, scheduling, professional qualification in APM or PRINCE2 in their advertisement for project manager roles.
- The study does not suggest that technical competencies are no longer relevant factors in project manager selection. Project management technical skills, although widely accepted as important, are considered to be baseline competencies. What can be concluded from the research findings is that the difference between an average project manager and a successful project manager is the extent to which they are competent in the so called soft people skills.
- Participants in this study indicated that leadership development does not necessarily have to be through formal training programmes but instead can be achieved through appropriate mentoring, shadowing and coaching.
- Development of project managers with strong leadership skills, as well as proficiency in project management methodologies, could result in improved project outcomes

The research objectives of this study have therefore been achieved; with project management competencies identified as being a project success factor for complex infrastructure projects.

The top 5 project management competencies identified in the study are presented in the table below:

Top 5 Project Management Competencies
Leadership – including having visions and goals
Communication skills - especially the ability to listen
Stakeholder management and team building skills
Ability to motivate and lead direct reports and project teams
Prior relevant experience

Table 18: Top 5 Project Management Competencies

5:2 Implications

Primary and secondary research findings suggest that project managers' leadership capability is an important factor in project success and deserves more attention with regards to training. This study has shown that project managers require leadership skills to be fully effective in delivering projects successfully. Their leadership skills development cannot be left to chance. The same rigour that is applied to technical project management training ought to be applied to leadership training to get 'well rounded' and effective project managers. The study indicates that many behavioural competencies are learned experientially. Therefore organisations need to assign the appropriate projects to individual project managers such that they are continually developing throughout their careers.

Although there is evidence to suggest that organisations have started to include the behavioural competencies and skills required of project managers in job and personnel specifications, there is still some work to be done in this regard. Knowing which behavioural competences are required and the degree of proficiency is essential for organisations when appointing project managers. This means that when recruiting project managers it is more pertinent for organisations to assess the behavioural skills of the individual than their technical project management knowledge.

It should be expected that the turbulent global economic environment will remain a source of challenge and change for many organisations across diverse sectors. Only organisations that successfully master the art of identification, selection, training, and development of project managers can expect to remain successful in delivering major capital projects.

Once project managers are in place, the organisation's senior management must develop and implement a mutually beneficial reward and reinforcement system that recognises that revenues are earned at the project level as well as operational level. In the long term, organisational leaders cannot be considered competent if the projects that generate stakeholder value fail.

The linkage between long-term organisational effectiveness and project management competence is aptly demonstrated by the figure below:

Figure 12: Relationship between project management competence and organisational performance

Source: Crawford, (2005)

With increasing complexity of project management environment, it is important for TfL and other organisations undertaking rail infrastructure projects to improve their project management personnel capability in order to achieve their strategic objectives. It is important therefore, that organisations develop a training programme for existing project managers and leaders. Because each organisation is unique, suitable training programmes and schemes should be developed taking into consideration its culture, politics and HR policies.

It is believed that this study has added to the body of knowledge in the area of project management leadership, notably in the rail industry. A better understanding of the impact of leadership skills on project outcomes may provoke a new approach to project managers' training and development.

5:3 Recommendations for Future Research

Based on the conclusions discussed above the following recommendations are offered:

1. Firstly, the growth of project management practice warrants the extension of the research scope beyond a single project management organisation and industry, first to a national level, and then to a global level
2. A study into what is an appropriate and effective methodology for reviewing project management competency is warranted. This would help identify the key steps in how an organisation might test competencies of their existing teams and develop appropriate strategies for developing their project management professionals.
3. A study of Project manager leadership styles, focusing on identifying which styles are appropriate for different project phases is recommended. Insights into effective project manager leadership techniques and styles could help address the social aspects of the project management construct.
4. Investigation of the impact of organisational culture on project performance or success is also recommended.

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APPENDIX

Appendix A: Informed Consent - Participants 18 Years of Age and Older

Dear XXXX,

I am a student at the University of Durham studying a Masters in Business Administration (MBA) degree. I am conducting a research study titled: "The Role of Project Management Competencies on Project Success in the Rail Industry".

Thank you for your interest in my research. I value the unique contribution that you can make to my dissertation and I am excited about the possibility of your participation in it.

The research will focus on gaining the insights from participants by examining their perceptions of the impact of project management and leadership competencies on project success, project success factors and project managers' leadership training.

I anticipate your participation will involve approximately 1 hour, in-person, semi-structured interview, with open-ended questions. The interviews will be scheduled at your convenience during April 2013.

Your participation is voluntary. If you choose not to participate or to withdraw from the study at any time, you can do so without penalty or loss of benefit to yourself. The results of the research study may be published but your identity will remain confidential and your name will not be disclosed to any outside party. You will also be asked to review the interview notes to validate the accuracy of the collected data.

You have a right to privacy, and all information identifying you will remain anonymous and confidential. Your answers secured during the interview process will be coded with numbers, and no identifying information will appear on any material.

In this research there are no foreseeable risks or direct benefits to you. However, the research may provide invaluable findings that may result in "best practice" for supporting project success in your organisation.

I value your participation and thank you for the commitment of time and effort. If you have any questions concerning this research or your participation, please call me on xxxx or send e-mail at xxxx. I hope that you will be able to serve as a participant in this study.

Yours sincerely,

XXXX XXXX

By signing this form, I acknowledge that I understand the nature of the study and the means by which my identity will be kept confidential. I am aware that I may withdraw from this study at any stage without any penalty to myself. My signature on this form indicates that I am 18 years or older and that I give permission to voluntarily serve as a participant in the study described.

SIGNATURE OF PARTICIPANT

DATE

Appendix B: MBA Dissertation Questionnaire

The questionnaire is structured into four sections namely: Section One – Demographic questions, Section Two – Project Management Competencies, Section Three - Top Five Competencies for Successful Projects and Section Four – Project Success Factors.

SECTION ONE – DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONS

1. Please indicate your discipline or functional area:

- a) Project management
- b) Engineering
- c) Planning
- d) Commercial
- e) Other

please specify:

2. What is your role within the project?

3. Please indicate your age category:

- a) 21-30
- b) 31-40
- c) 41-50
- d) 51 and over

4. What is your gender?

- a) Male
- b) Female

5. Highest educational level:

- a) Doctorate Degree
- b) Masters Degree
- c) Bachelors Degree
- d) NVQ/GCSE's

6. How many years have you worked in a project environment?

- a) Less than 5 years
- b) 5-15 years
- c) 15-20 years
- d) 20 years +

7. What is the typical duration of projects (from concept to completion) that you have worked in?

- a) Less than 2 years
- b) 2-4 years
- c) 4-6 years
- d) 6 years +

8. How many years have you been employed at your current organisation?

- a) Less than 5 years
- b) 5-10 years
- c) 10-20 years
- d) 20 years +

9. What is the average size of project teams you have worked in?

- a) 0-19
- b) 20-39
- c) 40-59
- d) 60 +

10. What is the average monetary value of the projects you have been involved in?

- a) Less than £1,000,000
- b) £1,000,000 - £5,000,000
- c) £5,000,000 -£100,000,000

d) £100,000,000 +

11. What is the average complexity of projects that you been involved within your current organisation, taking into account the tasks, deliverables, stakeholders, novelty of engineering solution etc?

- a) Low Complexity
- b) Medium Complexity
- c) High Complexity

SECTION TWO – PROJECT MANAGEMENT COMPETENCIES

From the list of competencies below, please rank the competencies that contributed to the successful implementation of the project/s that you have been involved in. Also categorise each factor into technical project management skills 'T', leadership skills 'L' or general management skills 'M'. If the competencies are not listed below, please state what the competencies are and also indicate which of the three categories it falls into.

On a scale of 1-4, where 1 is “not important”, 2 is “slightly important”, 3 is “quite important” and 4 is “very important”, please rank the following skills in their order of importance to project success* (See Note 1 below for definition of project success).						
Question No.	Project Management Competencies/Behaviours	1	2	3	4	Category T/L/M
12	Ability to develop clear project scope and manage the expectation of the business and stakeholders					
13	Ability to build and set out a clear project vision of what is to be accomplished with project team members' cooperation and support					
14	Good financial management/budgeting skills, and a good understanding of financial control and procurement processes.					
15	Ability to understand the core technology of the project deliverables					
16	Ability to effectively communicate project priorities, which align with the project goals and company objectives/values					

On a scale of 1-4, where 1 is “not important”, 2 is “slightly important”, 3 is “quite important” and 4 is “very important”, please rank the following skills in their order of importance to project success* (See Note 1 below for definition of project success).					
17	Ability to manage/lead and motivate multidisciplinary teams to deliver effective performance				
18	Ability to manage change				
19	Broad knowledge and understanding of commercial and contract issues in a technology and transport service environment				
20	Ability to remove obstacles and resolve conflicts				
21	Ability to complete cost estimates and produce project budget to support planning and decision-making				
22	Ability to effectively delegate tasks and empower others to make important decisions				
23	Exceptional organisational skills and the ability to manage multiple and conflicting priorities and make sound decisions in a high pressure environment				
24	Adopts a leadership style appropriate to the specific team and work situation				
25	Accepts total accountability, even when tasks are delegated				
26	Delivers on what was agreed to the required quality, on time and within budget				
27	Ability to identify resource requirements needed to support planning and decision-making				
28	Ability to effectively use project planning & control techniques to develop schedules and manage risks				
29	Ability to build strong working relationships with colleagues, clients and service providers				
30	A positive attitude and ability to deliver cost effective solutions when met with difficult and challenging project impacting risks and issues				
31	Ability to effectively present to senior management				
32	Ability to influence people at all levels across the organisation and outside, including negotiating and successfully facilitating joint decision making				
33	Ability to manage projects and conflicting priorities to				

On a scale of 1-4, where 1 is “not important”, 2 is “slightly important”, 3 is “quite important” and 4 is “very important”, please rank the following skills in their order of importance to project success* (See Note 1 below for definition of project success).						
	achieve tight deadlines					
34	Domain knowledge in the area of capital project management					
35	Ability to motivate and inspire project team members to perform better					
36	Professional qualification in Project or Programme Management, eg. APM, Prince 2 or MSP					
37	Ability to identify, evaluate, prioritise and manage risks (Safety, Commercial and potentially Environmental)					

Not listed, please indicate:

SECTION THREE – TOP FIVE COMPETENCIES

Rank the <u>top five competencies</u> that you perceive to be the most important for a project manager to be successful in implementing <u>complex rail infrastructure</u> projects and state why:		
Competencies	Competencies	Competencies
Leadership	Negotiation and Influencing Skills	Ability to work within a changing and ambiguous environment
Relevant prior experience	Risk management	Self confidence
Good knowledge of the core technology of the engineering solution	Project Planning & Control Techniques	Having visions and goals
Ability to motivate and lead direct reports and project teams	Emotional intelligence	Ability to work under pressure
Good communication and presentation skills	Stakeholder management	Excellent Interpersonal skills
Team building skills	Understanding of financial control and procurement processes and techniques	Problem solving skills

Not listed, please indicate:		
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Rank	Competencies	Comments
1		
2		
3		
4		
5		

SECTION FOUR – PROJECT SUCCESS FACTORS

On a scale of 1-4, where 1 is “not important”, 2 is “slightly important”, 3 is “quite important” and 4 is “very important”, please rank the following skills in their order of importance to project success (see Note 1 below for definition of project success).

Question No.	Project Success Factors	1	2	3	4	Category
						T/L/M
38	Project managers’ leadership skills (vision and motivating others)					
39	Skilled project team members					
40	Project team cohesiveness					
41	Management skills – including managing cross functional teams and stakeholders					
42	Effective decision-making and issue resolution					
43	Effective processes and procedures					
44	Clear roles and responsibilities					
45	Compelling vision, purpose and goals					
46	Effective planning and scheduling skills					
47	Project managers’ domain knowledge of core engineering solution					
48	Risk management skills					

Not listed, please indicate:

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Closing Statement to Participant:

Thank you very much for your participation in this survey.

Note 1: Project Success Definition

Over time, the definition of project success has evolved from factors associated with attaining the triple constraint to a comprehensive measure of project success that combines the project management measures of time, cost, and scope, with the product measures of client satisfaction, utilisation and benefit to the organization.

A project is considered an overall success if the project meets the technical performance specification (including safety) and/or mission to be performed, and if there is a high level of satisfaction concerning the project outcome among key people in the parent organization, key people in the project team and key users or clientele of the project effort (Baker et al (1983)).

Appendix C: Semi-Structured Interview Guide

Your participation in this interview is voluntary. If you choose not to participate or to withdraw from the interview at any time, you can do so without penalty or loss of benefit to yourself. The results of the research study may be published but your identity will remain confidential and your name will not be disclosed to any outside party.

You have a right to privacy, and all information identifying you will remain anonymous and confidential. Your answers secured during the interview process will be coded with numbers, and no identifying information will appear on any material.

1. Project success is defined by the Project Management Institute (2008) as the extent to which the project meets specific objectives within the constraints of resources, time, performance objectives as defined by the project stakeholders and the degree of customer satisfaction.
 - a) Do you agree with this definition?
 - b) If not, what is an appropriate definition of project success for rail infrastructure projects?
2. What do you consider to be the most important competencies for effective project managers and why?
3. In your view, is the project manager's leadership competence critical to project success?
 - a) If yes, explain why
 - b) If no, explain why
4. What are the key factors that contribute to the successful implementation of rail infrastructure projects?
5. Did you receive formal leadership training before or since assuming your present role? **Relevant to Project Managers only)**
 - a) If no, how would you say your leadership skills were developed?
 - b) Can project managers learn the skill of project leadership through on-the-job experience?
 - c) How do you think leadership training will enhance project managers' ability to deliver projects more successfully?
6. How can your organisation ensure that project managers have the relevant competencies to successfully deliver projects?

Was it through 360 degree feedback, mentoring & coaching, training courses, observation, on the job experience, Reading & Self Study, or Other?

7. What area/s do you think you as individual need to develop further as a project manager? **(Relevant to Project Managers only)**

- a) Technical project management skills
- b) Leadership skills

Closing Statement to Participant:

Thank you very much for your participation in this interview. If you think of any answers later that you would have liked to have given or would like to modify your answers let me know in the next 2 working days by email.

PROJECT MANAGEMENT COMPETENCIES		
Competencies	Competencies	Competencies
Leadership by example	Negotiation and Influencing Skills	Ability to work within a changing and ambiguous environment
Relevant prior experience	Risk management	Self confidence
Good knowledge of the core technology of the project deliverables	Scheduling and planning	Having visions and goals
Ability to motivate and lead direct reports and project teams	Emotional intelligence	Ability to work under pressure
Good communication and presentation skills	Stakeholder management	Excellent Interpersonal skills
Team building skills	Understanding of financial control and procurement processes and techniques	Problem solving skills

Appendix D: Survey Participants Demographics

Participants' age was grouped into four categories: 21 - 30, 31 - 40, 41 - 50, and older than 50. Majority of the participants were in the 31-40 age category, with 22 out of 47 participants belonging to that age group. This indicates that majority of respondents are fairly experienced but not necessarily in projects.

Appendix E: Session 4 Of Questionnaire Results

Question No.	Project Success Factors	Not Important %	Slightly Important %	Quite Important %	Very Important %
38	Project managers' leadership skills (vision and motivating others)	0.0	17.0	31.9	51.1
39	Skilled project team members	0.0	0.0	44.7	55.3
40	Project team cohesiveness	0.0	17.0	57.4	25.5
41	Management skills – including managing cross functional teams and stakeholders	0.0	17.0	38.3	44.7
42	Effective decision-making and issue resolution	0.0	17.0	29.8	53.2
43	Effective processes and procedures	12.8	14.9	40.4	31.9
44	Clear roles and responsibilities	0.0	19.1	31.9	48.9
45	Compelling vision, purpose and goals	14.9	21.3	25.5	38.3
46	Effective planning and scheduling skills	0.0	23.4	40.4	36.2
47	Project managers' domain knowledge of core engineering solution	14.9	21.3	38.3	25.5
48	Risk management skills	0.0	17.0	46.8	36.2
	Not listed				
	Safety Awareness				
	Listen first, take advice, then implement				

Appendix F: Delivery Schedule For TfL's Key Infrastructure Schemes

Project	2012 / 13	2013 / 14	2014 / 15	
Crossrail				▶ 2019
Tube				
Line upgrades				
Northern line				
Nothern line part 2				▶ Early 2020s
Northern line extension				▶ 2020
Sub-surface railway				▶ 2018
Future Tube upgrades				▶ 2020-30s
Congestion relief and station upgrade schemes				
Paddington (Hammersmith & City)				
Victoria				▶ 2018
Tottenham Court Road				▶ 2017
Bond Street				▶ 2017
Bank				▶ 2021
Surface Transport				
Hammersmith Flyover: phase 2 strengthening				
Bridge renewals				▶ 2016
Delivery of a further 600 New Bus for London vehicles				▶ 2016
SCOOT – roll-out to a further 1,500 sites				▶ 2019
Pedestrian Countdown - roll-out to a further 200 sites				
Tottenham Hale Gyrotory redevelopment				
Introduction of 1,300 electric vehicle charging points				
Better Junction review: safety improvement to 100 key junctions				▶ 2016
Completion of all 12 Barclays Cycle Superhighways				
Barclays Cycle Hire expansion and intensification				
Cycle hire system improvements				
Tramlink				
Platform works at Wimbledon				
Procurement of four additional trams				
London Overground				
Additional two trains per hour on the East London line				
Additional carriage on all lines:				
Gospel Oak Barking line				
East London line				
North and West London lines and Euston-Watford line				▶ 2016
DLR				
Double tracking of north route				▶ 2019
River				
Silvertown tunnel				▶ 2021
Other				
Contactless ticketing available on all modes				

TfL (2012): http://www.Tfl.Gov.Uk/Assets/Downloads/Corporate/Tfl-Business_Plan-2012.Pdf

Appendix G: London Underground Schedule of Projects

London Underground projects	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018
Electronic service update boards									
King's Cross congestion relief – phase II									
Wide-aisle gates installation									
Refurbishment of Silverlink stations complete									
Stratford station upgrade									
Southfields station step-free access									
West Ham station 2012 Games works									
Green Park station step-free access									
Finsbury Park station upgrade									
Northern line upgrade completed – phase I									
Metropolitan line upgrade completed									
Marble Arch station modernisation									
Notting Hill Gate modernisation									
Victoria line full upgrade completed									
Rayners Lane track capacity									
Piccadilly line upgrade completed									
Paddington station congestion relief									
Seven-car train project – trains in service									
Hammersmith & City line upgrade completed									
Sub-surface lines on-train air cooling									
Tottenham Court Road station									
Bond Street station congestion relief									
Victoria station upgrade									
LU line upgrades – Circle line upgrade completed									

(TfL: <http://www.TfL.gov.uk/assets/downloads/corporate/TfL-investment-programme-introduction.pdf>).

Appendix H: Shenhar et al.'s (1997) Multi-Dimensional Framework of Project Success

<p>Success Dimension 1-Project Efficiency</p> <p>The first dimension is the short-term measure expressing the efficiency, with which the project process has been managed. It simply tells us whether the project was completed on time and within the specified budget. This is the immediate dimension with which the project can be assessed, first during execution, and immediately after completion. Although success in this dimension may indicate a well-managed, efficient project, it may not indicate success in the long-term nor benefit to the organization. However, with increased competition and shorter product life cycles, time-to-market (time from initial concept to market introduction) becomes a critical competitive component. Enhanced project efficiency should therefore be seen as adding to product competitiveness.</p>	<p>Success Dimension 2-Impact on the Customer</p> <p>The second dimension relates to the customer and/or the user of the end result. This dimension addresses the importance organizations should place on customer requirements and real needs. As our results indicate, meeting performance measures, functional requirements, and technical specifications are all part of this second dimension, and not, as previously assumed, part of meeting the project plan. From the contractor's point of view, this dimension also includes the level of customer satisfaction, the extent to which the customer is using the product, and whether the customer is willing to come back for a follow-up project or for buying the next generation of the same product</p>
<p>Success Dimension 3-Business and Direct Success</p> <p>The third dimension addresses the direct impact the project may have on the organization. In the business context, did it provide sales, income, and profits as expected? Did it help increase business results and gain market share? However, this dimension may also apply to projects not aimed at building new products. For example, internal reengineering projects</p>	<p>Success Dimension 4-Preparing for the Future</p> <p>The fourth dimension addresses preparing organizational and technological infrastructure for the future. It is the longest-term dimension and involves the following questions: How does the organization prepare for future opportunities? Does it explore new opportunities for further markets, ideas, innovations and products? Does it build new skills that may be needed in the future, or develop new technologies and core</p>

<p>(Hammer & Champy, 1993) or the development of a new manufacturing process also need assessment. This is the measure with which such an assessment could be made. It will include measures of performance time, cycle time, yield, and quality of the process, and total improvement of organizational performance. All of these will assess the direct impact the project had on the organization.</p>	<p>competencies? Is it prepared to make a change and create the future in its industry or to adapt quickly and meet additional challenges, unexpected moves of competitors, and market and technology surprises?"</p>
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Appendix I: Evolution of Leadership Theories

Great Man Theories	Based on the belief that leaders were exceptional people, born with innate qualities, destined to lead. The use of the term “man” was intentional since until the latter part of the twentieth century, leadership was of as a concept that is primarily male, military and Western. This led to the next school of Trait theories.
Trait Theories	The list of traits or qualities associated with leadership exist in abundance and continue to be produced. They draw on virtually all the adjectives in the dictionary which describe some positive or virtuous human attribute, from ambition to zest for life.
Behaviourist Theory	These concentrate on what leaders actually do rather than on their qualities. different patterns of behaviour are observed and categorised as styles of leadership. This area has probably attracted the most attention from practicing managers.
Situational Leadership	This approach sees leadership as specific to the situation in which it is being exercised. For example, whilst some situations may require an autocratic style, others may need a more participatory approach. it also proposes that there may be differences in required leadership styles at different levels in the same organisation.
Contingency Theory	This is a refinement of the situational viewpoint and focuses on identifying the situational variables which best predict the most appropriate or effective leadership style to fit the particular circumstances.
Transactional Theory	This approach emphasises the importance of the relationship between leader and followers, focusing on the mutual benefits derived from a form of “contract” through which the leader delivers such things as rewards or recognition in return for the commitment or loyalty of the followers.
Transformational Theory	The central concept here is change and the role of the leadership in envisioning and implementing the transformation of organisational performance.

Adapted from: Bolden et al (2003) “A Review of Leadership Theory and Competency Frameworks”